

PENNSYLVANIA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET

$$\begin{matrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

TASK 3: PILOT MODEL STUDY

CONTRACT #355I01

ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET

Category #05 - Environmental Research

$$\bar{x} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

April 2014

URS

$$(x + a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^k a^{n-k}$$

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ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET
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ABSTRACT

This report is the documentation for Task 3 of the Statewide Archaeological Predictive Model Set project sponsored by the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation (PennDOT). This project was solicited under Contract #355I01, Transportation Research, Education, and Technology Transfer ITQ, Category #05 – Environmental Research. The goal of this project is to develop a set of statewide predictive models to assist the planning of transportation projects. PennDOT is developing tools to streamline individual projects and facilitate Linking Planning and NEPA, a federal initiative requiring that NEPA activities be integrated into the planning phases for transportation projects. The purpose of Linking Planning and NEPA is to enhance the ability of planners to predict project schedules and budgets by providing better environmental and cultural resources data and analyses. To that end, PennDOT is sponsoring research to develop a statewide set of predictive models for archaeological resources to help project planners more accurately estimate the need for archaeological studies.

The objective of Task 3 is to create a series of archaeological predictive models for a pilot study region. This task is designed to be a dry-run of the modeling process that will be applied to the entire Commonwealth. Through this task, many foreseen and unforeseen issues were discovered and addressed. This task involved a number of steps: 1) data collection; 2) data preparation; 3) segmenting study area; 4) creation of judgmentally weighted model (Model Class 1); 5) evaluation of discriminant variables; 6) creation of proportionally weighted model (Model Class 2); 7) creation of a series of regression/classification models (Model Class 3); 8) model testing and compilation. The outcome of this process is a series of site location sensitivity GIS raster layers and model metrics that will be used to judge the efficacy and reliability of each specific region. Additional outcomes of the pilot model task are a series of recommendations and procedures that will be implemented during the full-scale modeling of Pennsylvania. This report provides the background information, methodological procedures, model outcomes, and recommendations.

The final model ensemble for the entire pilot model area correctly classified 85% of the known archaeological site area into either high (72%) or moderate (13%) sensitivity. Conversely, high and moderate sensitivity covers 6.7% and 9.6% of the pilot model study area, respectively. This yields a Kvamme gain statistic of 0.82. The 10 sub-models used to create this ensemble are built with assumptions commensurate with the sub-regions' data quality and with metrics for model fit, stability, and prediction error. Overall, the procedures and methods created through the pilot model study were successful and should be implemented on a state-wide basis with some modification.

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INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this project is to use the existing Pennsylvania Archaeological Site Survey file database (PASS)* to produce a baseline model for the sensitivity of prehistoric site-presence throughout the entire Commonwealth. The resulting assessments of archaeological sensitivity will be used by transportation, planning, and other Cultural Resource Management (CRM) practitioners to make better-informed and more consistent assessments of prehistoric archaeological sensitivity, with the ultimate goal of saving time, money, and sparing cultural resources.

Achieving this goal requires many hurdles to be overcome, including the vast size of the state, the locational bias present in the PASS database, processing enormous amounts of data, and the methodological challenges of creating statistical models that attempt to predict archaeologically sensitive locations. In order to address these hurdles, a pilot study was done in a small, representative area of the state consisting of four counties in central Pennsylvania: Blair, Centre, Clearfield, and Clinton. The processes that were established during the pilot study, and the lessons learned along the way, will be incorporated into the statewide models that will be developed in the next phase of the project.

The approach that was developed through the pilot model relies on the use of a multi-level model-building sequence, a series of statistical measures to assess model fit and predictive ability, portioning of the study area based on hydrology and physiography, and a conservative approach to assessing PASS data quality. The end result is a method that is able to produce models of prehistoric archaeological sensitivity over large areas that are congruent with variations in site location data quality and are accompanied by metrics to aid in the interpretation of model performance.

* Appendix A provides a list of acronyms and a glossary of terms used in the text.

MISSION AND PHILOSOPHY

“Essentially, all models are wrong, but some are useful.”

—Box and Draper (1987)

Scientific models are used to gain better understandings of systems by focusing on specific variables and mechanisms to the exclusion of others. The parts of the system that are focused upon are developed into a schematic that is intended to approximate the system in the hopes of understanding it through simplicity. Those factors removed from the schematic may add little to the overall system or may be of a level of complexity that cannot be easily addressed. If testing shows that the schematic model is a decent approximation, it may be used to explore unobserved parts of the system or better explain existing observations. If the schematic model is shown to be a poor approximation of the overall system, it may be due to a number of reasons: poor choice of representative factors; the overall system is not well documented; or the complexity of the system defies the tools at hand.

As captured by Box’s quote above, all models being approximations are inherently wrong because none can encapsulate the entire system’s dynamics in total. To do that, it would cease to be a model and investigators would have run out of tools and computers well before that point is reached. Box continues the sentiment above by stating that the true measure of a model is not whether it is right or wrong, but rather how wrong can it be before it loses its utility. This conveys the notion that the “right” model may not yet exist or not be achievable given current techniques, but a useful model is the least “wrong” of the available candidate models and has utility in achieving the established goals; this can be thought of as the “best” model available.

In the form of Archaeological Predictive Modeling (APM) used in this project, the target of our approximation is the known location of prehistoric archaeological sites: that is, the settlement pattern. This pattern was generated through an endlessly complex and relatively poorly understood settlement system, a system that had operated for nearly 15,000 years and was subject to unknowable cultural and natural factors. Furthermore, the pattern of archaeological remains produced by the settlement system has been acted upon by thousands of years of natural systems that have obscured, exposed, and reshaped the site pattern we see today. Finally, the fragments of the site pattern we known today are only a reflection of our relatively modern land-use and recordation systems. Through this, it is understood that the models generated by studying the known settlement pattern can only be representative of a fraction of what is to be known. Albeit far from perfect, however, any schematic model that can approximate a portion of the settlement pattern with some confidence will be useful in extrapolating that pattern to areas beyond those previously observed.

The approach employed in this project seeks to use statistical methods and environmental data to formalize the known settlement pattern and extrapolate it across the landscape. In theory, this approach attempts to model the portion of the Native American settlement system that was influenced by decisions based on environmental constraints or cultural factors that had a significant environmental component. Clearly, there are uncountable cultural and social factors that influenced prehistoric settlement decisions. It is these and the aforementioned effects of natural and modern cultural systems that are the primary sources of uncertainty that influence our models and require consideration in the interpretation of the results. The models in this project do not attempt to quantify past human behavior, but instead they learn from the locations at which the expressions of past behaviors are evident as material culture.

This approach is decidedly empirical/inductive in nature and functions from “the ground up.” As such, this approach seeks to use site locations as the primary observations from which the settlement pattern is extracted. Site locations serve as the principal means to segment the landscape into areas that are prehistoric archaeological sites from those that are not; their density and dispersion in an area serve as the decision criteria for which model to use; and finally they serve as the means by which predictions are tested and validated. That is not to say that elements of the deductive, or theory-based, approaches are not incorporated when site data are limited or non-existent. Throughout the history of implementing predictive, forecasting, and sensitivity analysis models in archaeology there has been lively debate regarding which is the “best” approach to attain the goal of predicting the likelihood of archaeological material in unsurveyed areas (for an in-depth discussion see Kohler and Parker [1986], and for a short wrap-up see Verhagen and Whitley [2012]). From this debate, two of the most common criticisms leveled at data-driven models are that these models lack explanatory power and that the bias inherent in using known site locations leads to circular predictions. In many senses, both of these criticisms are true and arguably could be leveled at models produced from either theoretical camp. While the modeling approach employed in this project is intended to be value pragmatism over ideology, the numerous caveats of data-driven modeling are acknowledged and pains are taken to control for bias and quantify uncertainty when present and accountable.

The pilot model-building process revealed many unforeseen issues and found ways to overcome or work around the majority of them. This report will walk through the modeling process developed here, illuminate the solutions that were applied, and make recommendations for methods to implement from here onward. Undoubtedly, new issues will appear and new challenges will be confronted. The models produced to this point appear to achieve the goals outlined above and are well in-line with, if not surpassing, the results of the successful models outlined in Task 1 of this project. This is not to say that these models are without fault or cannot be improved upon. Throughout this project, a number of recommendations will be made for

ways to improve the modeling methods, better utilize site data, and advance the controls for bias. The basis for some of these recommendations will only be discovered through completing the modeling process, while others will already be known but simply unrealistic to apply to the initial running of a model of this scope.

It is hoped that the legacy of this project is the stimulation of research and advancement in new and better modeling approaches. It is also hoped that this is only a starting point from which the collection of new data and the development of better model methods can build. The areas at which these models poorly fit the archaeological record can serve as points of discussion and a basis for the development of a better understanding of modeling techniques and site location dynamics. Conversely, where the models fit well, the statistical correlations and metrics can be explored to see if new information on settlement systems can be found. The archaeological sensitivity models generated through this project will serve a valuable purpose as tools for planning, assessment, and cost-control; hopefully this is not the end, but only the beginning.

MODELING APPROACH

The approach taken to producing digital representations of prehistoric archaeological sensitivity can be generalized into three main steps: 1) data preparation; 2) model creation and testing (which includes model building and testing-validation); and 3) model selection and finalization. Some of the routines within each of these steps are standardized and repeatedly applied in each region, while other steps involve decision boundaries and need to be supervised each step of the way. The discussion below will give an overview of the generalized modeling process and point out the locations at which user input is required. Additional details of the specifics of each step will be introduced further on in this report.

The simple theory that guides the steps to creating sensitivity assessments is that the pattern of known archaeological sites relative to the environment is an indicator of where unknown archaeological sites may be found. Further, that by finding strong environmental correlations, this pattern can be separated from background noise and extrapolated across the landscape using one or a variety of statistical models. And finally, that the expression of this pattern through statistical models can be tested for how well it fits the known data and predicts independent data, thereby assessing its utility. Each step of the process, schematized in Figure 1, is implemented with this theory in mind and the goal of producing well-fit models that have the ability to identify known site locations and adhere to regional understandings of settlement dynamics.

DATA PREPARATION

Data from three main sources are prepared during this stage: PASS database, Pennsylvania Historical and Museum Commission (PHMC) survey data, and environmental background data. These are the data from which the model is built, and therefore standardization and quality checking in this processing step are very important. Quality checking not only helps us to understand the data better, but also helps avoid the problem of propagating errors throughout the remainder of the steps.

Archaeological Site Locations

The data received from the PHMC includes the spatial representation (GIS files) of archaeological site locations and previous cultural resources survey boundaries, and a Microsoft Access relational database with attributes for each site and survey. The data model for the complete Cultural Resources Geographic Information System (CRGIS) database for survey, archaeological sites, and historic resources includes 66 interrelated tables. The survey and archaeological site subset database used for this project contains 29 interrelated tables that contain information regarding, but not limited to, site name, geology, excavation methods, time

Figure 1 - Schematic of general model-building process used in this project.

periods, National Register of Historic Places status, and artifact types. The tables for survey locations include identification information on the survey report, location, and character of the survey area.

For the pilot model, the preparation of the archaeological site data was relatively simple. Initially, the database was split based on sites that contained a prehistoric component and those

that did not. Site locations that recorded only a historic-period archaeological component were excluded from this study. The designation of a site containing a prehistoric component was established using the ARTIFACT and CHRONOLOGY tables in the database. Any site that contained a Paleoindian through Late Woodland or general Prehistoric component in the CHRONOLOGY table was included. Additionally, any site that included prehistoric lithic tools or ceramics listed in the ARTIFACT table was included. There was a high degree of fidelity between these two tables. The GIS shapefile representing archaeological site locations was joined with the attribute data denoting prehistoric components and all sites that lacked a prehistoric component were removed. The modeling process from this point on utilized this shapefile of prehistoric components.

Environmental Background Data

The preparation of the environmental background data involved the collection of primary data sources, the creation of secondary data variables, and the statistical testing of these variables to demonstrate their ability to discriminate site locations from the background. The selection of which background variables to subject to this testing is guided by the availability of environmental data, environmental parameters that fit our understanding of settlement systematics, and limiting bias based on selective survey and modern disturbances to the landscape. A total of 70 background variables were created for the pilot model study. Appendix B provides a description of each variable.

The primary data sources used to create the variables are elevation, in form of a 1/3rd Arc second resolution (10.48770145 m) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), and a series of hydrological datasets including stream, wetlands, and water bodies. The first step is to prepare the primary data sources by eliminating clearly modern water features and creating a “depressionless” DEM by filling in micro-topographic anomalies, what are called “sinks.” From these primary datasets, the secondary variables are derived. The initial secondary variables include simple calculations of topographic slope, aspect, and Euclidian distance to water features. Further calculation that utilizes a search radius (called a neighborhood) is required to derive additional measures of the landscape. Such variables include the mean or standard deviation of slope within a 16-cell neighborhood. Compound variables are calculated through statistical operations on two or more other variables; these include Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) (Pathak 2010) and Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI) (Riley et al. 1999). Other compound measures include calculating the difference in elevation from features such as stream heads or confluences. Finally, cost variables are created that incorporate “cost” of traveling over certain barriers to reach an objective. These variables acknowledge that the best available route to an objective, such as a stream, is not always the shortest route. Typically in APM, and also utilized here, the primary cost used in these calculations is topographic slope, but additional costs such as wetlands or soil types may be employed.

Variables range from basic to relatively complex measures of the environment and serve as the pool from which statistical tests select those variables that show the greatest ability to differentiate the location of archaeological sites from the greater environmental background. The specific tests used to find discriminant variables are the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K-S) test and the Mann-Whitney (MW) U test. Generally speaking, both are non-parametric tests that measure the dissimilarity of two distributions; in this case the distributions are environmental variables measured at known site locations and those randomly picked from the background. There are specific differences in each test that contribute information valuable to understanding the way in which the two samples are different. Within each region modeled, each of the 70 variables (including a purely random noise variable) is tested against 100 random samples of 50,000 background values. The results are tabulated and the test statistics and p-values are compared to identify those variables that are most discriminant, as well as indications of how site location patterns are expressed within the variable pool. From the list of the most discriminant variables, a number (generally 3–5) are chosen to represent the different classes of variables in the modeling process. Classes of variables are multiple variables that measure variations of the same thing such as slope within a neighborhood. Only one variable within a class is chosen to represent that class, thus reducing the correlation of explanatory variables.

MODEL CREATION AND TESTING

The model-building procedure in this overall sequence is the point at which the pattern inferred from site locations is extracted from the variables and applied to the landscape of the project area. This can be done by a bewildering variety of methods, some employing simple arithmetic and others relying on intricate statistics, each with their own advantages and drawbacks. For this project, the approach selected is to allow the site data quality to determine the type of model that is applied. This is in opposition to picking a standardized model type and applying it to the entire project area regardless of data quality. The latter approach would allow for more consistent comparison and replication of the results across the study area, whereas the former allows for the incorporation of data quality variability, thereby finding the model type that best represents the data and allowing for better fitting model results. Based on this approach, a three-tiered model hierarchy was created. This hierarchy consisted of a base model (Model Class 1), an intermediate model (Model Class 2), and a high-level model (Model Class 3). Base models (Model Class 1) were applied to the entire pilot model study area, whereas intermediate and high-level models (Model Class 2 and Model Class 3) were only applied where more than 10 sites were recorded within the modeled area.

The following descriptions of each method are intended to be generalized introductions that outline the approaches to each model type. In the following chapters, the more technical parts of each model will be illustrated through examples from the pilot model dataset. It is beyond the

scope of this study to fully elaborate on the specifics of the more sophisticated statistical models. The references within the text and glossary should be consulted to gain a deeper understanding of the statistical mechanisms underpinning each method.

Model Class 1 – Judgmentally Weighted

The base model, Model Class 1, is represented by a simple judgmentally weighted additive sum model using two variables: topographic slope and distance to streams and water bodies. These two variables represent the most basic of environmental constraints and are intended to function as estimators of habitable locations in the absence of a sufficient sample of known archaeological site locations. The model functions by dividing each variable into five classes and then assigning sensitivity weights to each of the classes. For every 10 × 10-m cell in the study area, the applicable weights for the two variables are summed; the higher values presume higher archaeological sensitivity.

Assuming the settlement pattern of every area would not be equally represented by the same series of weights, five different weighting schemes were developed for each variable. The distribution from each weighting scheme represents a different dynamic that may capture changes in settlement based on different environments or settlement systems. In the example shown in Table 1, the five classes for slope and distance to water are shown across the first row, and the weights are shown in the rows below, one row for each of the five weighting schemes.

Table 1 - Weighting Schemes for Variables in Model Class 1 of the Pilot Study

Topographic slope (percent)					
Slope	0 - 3	3 - 5	5 - 8	8 - 15	15+
Scheme 1	10	5	3	2	0
Scheme 2	9	8	2	1	0
Scheme 3	8	6	4	2	0
Scheme 4	8	9	2	1	0
Scheme 5	7	8	3	2	0

Distance to streams or water bodies (meters)					
Hydrology	0 - 100	100 - 200	200 - 400	400 - 800	800+
Scheme 1	15	8	4	2	1
Scheme 2	12	10	5	2	1
Scheme 3	10	8	6	4	2
Scheme 4	9	14	4	2	1
Scheme 5	8	12	6	3	1

Figure 2 - Schematic of the summation of judgmental weighting schemes process in Model Class 1.

A new raster is created for each of the five weighting schemes, resulting in 10 new layers—five different versions of both slope and distance to water. Each of the five different schemes for slope weights is paired with each of the five different schemes for distance to water, resulting in 25 unique combinations representing sensitivity for each 10 × 10-m cell within the project area (Figure 2). The selection of the best model to represent the area can be chosen by a combination of methods: visually inspecting the model results against the known site locations, consulting regional settlement pattern studies, and comparing the distribution of sensitivity values to neighboring areas with larger site samples but comparable environments. The results of this type of model are difficult to validate given the lack of site location data in the region to which they

are applied. They can, however, be corroborated with theory and site locations that share similar settlement patterns and environments.

Model Class 2 – Proportionally Weighted

The second class of models are applied to areas that contain a sufficient number of known site locations. For the pilot model, areas with more than 10 sites were modeled using this approach. A proportionally weighted model, unlike the judgmentally weighted Model Class 1, uses the location of known sites to guide the selection and weighting of variables. A schematic of the Model Class 2 process is illustrated in Figure 3.

The variables selected to represent the site settlement pattern in each modeled region are those that show the best evidence for discrimination against background values. The ability to discriminate is based on the K-S test and MW U test, as described in the data preparation section, above. After selecting the appropriate discriminatory variables, the distribution of values for each selected variable is calculated for all site-present grid cells within the region. The actual sensitivity weights are assigned to each variable by dividing it into 10 classes based on the histogram of the distribution. The classes are determined using Sturges's formula of bin selection (Sturges 1926). The percentage of total site-present cells that each class represents is calculated, and weights are assigned to each of the 10 classes; in the case of the pilot model, the weight values fell within the 0–20 range, though any range could be used. The class with the highest percentage gets the highest weight of 20, the lowest percentage gets a weight of 0, and the remaining weights are distributed accordingly. For example, a variable measuring the distance from third-order streams may have 65% of the site-present cells occurring between the distances of 50–150 m. With no other range of distances containing a higher proportion of site-present cells, the class for 50–150 m is assigned a sensitivity weight of 20.

Following the establishment of sensitivity values, the raster GIS layers that represent each of the selected variables are reclassified with the corresponding sensitivity values. As such, each variable raster represents a continuous surface of sensitivity values corresponding to proportion of sites. Using the example above, the raster layer for distance to water would be reclassified such that all of the cells that lie between 50 and 150 m from a third-order stream are given a value of 20, and likewise for the remaining weights. After all of the raster layers are reclassified with the corresponding weights, the layers are summed to equal a composite sensitivity for all variables.

Figure 3 - Schematic of the steps to create the proportionally weighted models.

To finalize the model, the distribution of sensitivity values from within known sites is compared to a large sample of sensitivity background values. The cumulative frequencies for both site-present and background cells are computed, and from these the Kvamme Gain (Kg) statistic is derived and tabulated. In this use, the Kg is a continuous value that ideally is highest (closest to 1) for the highest summed sensitivity value and decreases with decreasing sensitivity values. Using the Kg along with the cumulative frequencies of sensitivity values for site-present cells and background cells, the model's cut-points are established. This can be visualized by a cross-over graph, an example of which is shown in Figure 4. Sensitivity values from the composite layer (x-axis) and their cumulative frequency as a percentage of the total number of cells (y-axis) are graphed for site-present cells (blue line) and background cells (red line). Additionally, the trend of the Kg statistic is shown using a secondary y-axis. The optimal point at which to split predicted site-presence from absence is at or near the crossing of the site present (blue) and background (red) lines. A Kg of about 0.71 would result from using the optimal cut point of about 44 to divide the prediction. However, these models are segmented into high, moderate, and low sensitivity, not present vs. absent, so the cross-over is used more as a guide than a rule.

Figure 4 - Example of cross-over graphic of model outcome and trend in Kg.

Model Class 3 – Statistical Models

The class referred to as Model Class 3 is actually a collection of models that share the quality of being statistically based and geared toward regression. The previously discussed model types are statistical in the sense that they use quantitative data and arithmetic to make assessments of prehistoric site location sensitivity. The types of Model Class 3 are more appropriately described as statistical, however, in that they use more sophisticated approaches to assessing sensitivity and employ hypothesis testing and other mathematical metrics to determine their fit, discrimination, and validity. The three principal model types used are logistic regression (LR), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) (Friedman 1991), and Random Forests (Breiman 2001).

These statistical models require a high degree of data quality and a great deal of effort, but they have the potential to yield the best performing and most accurate assessments of prehistoric site sensitivity. Conversely, these models also have the greatest potential to offer errant results that are difficult to interpret, thereby requiring constant attention to detail and consistent verification. Figure 5 illustrates a schematic of the process developed to address the challenges of model assessment, validation, and selection. Through this process hundreds, if not thousands, of models are created and tested for each region. Techniques such as K-folds Cross-Validation (CV) and bootstrapping are used to collect model metrics from many different selections and random permutations of the available data. These metrics are then analyzed over many different runs to better understand model stability in the face of changing parameters and independent data. After thousands of model runs and assessment of model fit and prediction error estimations, the remaining candidate models are applied to the entire study area. This involves using the combination of raster layers at each cell location in the GIS to predict the probability of archaeological site occurrence for each cell. The outcome is a continuous surface predicting the probability of site occurrence across the landscape. The probability rasters are tabulated as they were in Model Class 2, and cross-over graphs and Kg statistics are calculated. The final model is selected from the candidates, or in some cases created by combining candidate models to best capitalize on their individual strengths or compensate for variations in fit.

Figure 5 - Schematic of modeling and validation process used for Model Class 3.

There are hundreds of books and articles dedicated to the particulars of the three model types employed here. A full discourse is not within the scope of this report, but an introduction to the concepts that guide each is provided here and more details will be introduced later on. The LR model is a long-standing and de facto model in many fields of study for understanding the relationship between predictor variables and a dichotomous response variable (e.g., in archaeology, site presence or absence). Its use in archaeology extends back to the beginnings of statistical modeling in the field (Kvamme 1988). The more common linear regression models use continuous response variables and therefore are not well suited to predicting presence or absence. In cases where a researcher is attempting to predict site densities within a region, or understand variation within ceramic vessel sizes, then a linear model may be appropriate. The logistic model solves the problem of unbounded linear predictions (i.e., not limited to two set values as required in a dichotomous response variable) by replacing the linear relationship with the logit function. The logit function is an S-shaped curve that transforms the effects of the predictor variables on the dichotomous response, thereby bounding them between zero and one. This occurs by applying the logit transformation to the response variable (y) and using the predictors (x) to predict the logit, or log odds, of y . By linearizing the inherently non-linear relationship between x and y , the logit transformation function of the logistic model allows for the prediction of bounded probabilities for a dichotomous response, such as site-presence vs. absence. For comparison, Figure 6 is a linear regression (black line) fitted to a dichotomous response variable (black circles) and Figure 7 is the S-shaped logit function fitted to the same dichotomous response (the pattern of black circles appears different because the drawing program automatically offsets them vertically from one another to avoid overlap; in fact, all circles have a value of either zero or one). Note that while the linear regression example shown in Figure 6 extends beyond zero and one (i.e., it is unbounded), the logit function shown in Figure 7 does not (i.e., it is bounded).

The second of the Model Class 3 models in this project is called MARS, developed by Jerome H. Friedman (Friedman 1991). MARS is a trademark registered to Salford Systems and implementations of this method outside of Salford System's software must therefore go by a different name. For this project, we utilized the implementation of this technique by Stephen Milborrow (2011) called "Earth." Throughout this report, this technique will be referred to as Earth or adaptive regression splines, but all references will be discussing the same technique developed by Friedman.

Figure 6 - Example of linear fitted model to dichotomous response variable.

Figure 7 - Example of Logit function fitted to dichotomous response variable.

The adaptive regression spline model implemented in Earth is a non-parametric regression analysis that can be adapted to the family of Generalized Linear Models (GLM), which contain LR, and therefore can be used to predict the probabilities of a dichotomous response (e.g., site presence or absence). The objective of the adaptive regression spline model is to capture the non-linear relationships between the response (e.g., site presence or absence) and the predictors (e.g., variables) in a way that produces a continuous model, is computationally efficient, and lends to interpretation. In a general sense, the Earth algorithm fits the non-linear relationship between variables with a series of linear splines. These splines are connected by what are called “hinge functions” that describe the angle between two splines. In this way, a wavy line describing two variables can be modeled by a series of shorter straight lines and hinges. Figure 8 is a simple example of the fitted splines from the Earth algorithm utilizing the same data in Figure 7. The fitted black line is made up of numerous smaller linear splines and takes on a similar form to the logistic model in Figure 7, but is not confined to the same S-shaped form; it can therefore achieve a better fit. The original response data points at one and zero are the same as in Figure 7 and the remaining figures. Other important aspects of the Earth algorithm are that it incorporates optimization through forwards and backwards passes (hence the term adaptive in the trademarked, MARS name), and estimates performance with Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV). To this author’s knowledge, there are no published references of this algorithm being used in APM. Uses in other related predictive studies include Leathwick and Hastie (2006) predicting species distribution; Felicísimo and Gómez-Muñoz (2007) comparing the MARS method to other models for forest management; and most recently, Felicísimo et al. (2012) on the use of MARS, Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and other models in mapping landslide susceptibility. Additional papers using MARS have been published in the fields of biology, ecology, and geography.

The final model that was employed in the pilot study is called Random Forests (Breiman 2001). As was the case with the MARS model, the term “Random Forests” is trademarked to its creators, Leo Breiman and Adele Cutler. The implementation of the model used in this project was developed by Andy Liaw and Matthew Wiener (2002) and called randomForest. The remainder of this text will simply use the acronym RF to describe this technique. The RF model is a tree-based regression method that builds off a similar model called Bootstrap Aggregating, or Bagging. The core component of this method is the creation of a single decision tree. This term is used because the graphical representation of the model resembles a tree in that there is a trunk containing the sample observations, followed by a split into two branches, which are then each split into two branches, etc., forming a dendritic network that resembles a tree. The RF algorithm creates numerous (hundreds to thousands) of these tree models for each data set, and the predictions are calculated by the results from all of the trees. RF is called an ensemble method because it uses many models to come to a consensus. This is also the source of the “forest” part of the name.

Figure 8 - Example of adaptive regression splines fitted to dichotomous response variable.

Within an RF model there is any number of individual tree models. Each individual tree takes a random selection of the presence/absence data as a training sample and a random selection of the predictor variables. From this, the tree grows based on parameters that guide how each branch splits and how many observations end up in each class. As the tree grows, it tries to optimize the value at which each branch splits so that the resulting predictions match the left-over testing sample (termed the Out-Of-Bag [OOB] sample). After this tree is grown and its prediction error rate is known, another tree is grown with a randomly selected training and testing set, as well as a new random set of variables. This tree is grown in the same way and the prediction error, called the OOB error, is recorded. Repeating this process for anywhere from 500 to thousands of trees, the model is able to recognize the particular combinations of predictor variable values that lead to the lowest OOB prediction error. Further, by introducing random splitting at branches, the model is able to identify how important each predictor is to the overall success of the model. The resulting prediction is generated by averaging the prediction of all of the trees in the forest.

Following the previous examples, Figure 9 shows the same dichotomous response variable with a fitted RF model. Clearly this is non-linear and is very flexible in segmenting the variable space. Benefits to using the RF model are that it is a very accurate learning algorithm, it produces

internal estimates of error rates, it can handle very large datasets, and it is relatively efficient computationally. This model is capable of over-fitting data, however, or at least fitting too tight for comfort, and is more difficult to interpret regarding variable interaction and effect. To this author's knowledge, there is a single published example of the RF model used in APM. Märker and Heydari-Guran (2009) used this method with success in a test case based on Paleolithic site locations in the Zagros Mountains of southern Iran. An example of its use in a related field is Menze and Ur's (2012) mapping of long-term settlement changes in northern Mesopotamia. Perhaps of most interest are Oehlert and Shea's (2007) recommendations for the planned Phase 4 of the Mn Model. In their report, Oehlert and Shea evaluate a number of statistical models that could be used to improve upon the LR model used in the existing implementation of the statewide model. They conclude with the observation that the tree model techniques, such as boosting and bagging, provide superior results over the other regression methods. The authors could only recommend a stripped down version of the tree model, however, because they had not yet found a way to implement it along with a GIS. That barrier is no longer present, and the RF model implemented here is the next generation of the tree models Oehlert and Shea found great success in.

Figure 9 - Example of RF model fitted to dichotomous response variable.

MODEL SELECTION AND FINALIZATION

At the conclusion of the model building stage, there will be perhaps dozens of models that represent the sensitivity of archaeological site locations across the study area. The judgmentally weighted Model Class 1 will cover the entire region, the proportionally weighted Model Class 2 and the various permutations of regression models from Model Class 3 will cover sub-areas that have at least 10 known sites. From this collection of candidate models, final models must be selected to represent each area. This is done through a quantitative comparison of model metrics and a more qualitative analysis of model fit vis-à-vis the distribution of archaeological sites and project goals.

The process of model selection begins with assessing the data quality of each sub-region within the study area. In sub-areas with fewer than 10 sites, the known site sample is insufficient to model using regression or tree-based methods. Unless the sub-area is quite small, modeling with these methods would produce results that are unstable and have high variance and, therefore, their ability to predict new site locations would be questionable. In areas with limited data quality, one of the permutations of the weighting schemes of Model Class 1 is selected to serve as a baseline assessment of sensitivity based on simple principles: level ground and proximity to water. Without the presence of documented archaeological sites within some modeled areas, it is impossible to gauge the quantitative ability of the model to correctly classify sites. Nonetheless, the various candidate models can be reviewed, visually inspected against the study area, and assessed to see which weighting schemes make the most sense given the area's topography and hydrology. The model selected from the candidates is then classified into high, moderate, and low sensitivity based on any sites within the region or neighboring region, or by judgment alone.

In areas with more than 10 sites, it is assumed that the site sample is adequate to attempt to apply the results from Model Class 2 or Model Class 3. A number of metrics are used to determine which models best represent the data of each sub-region. The various types of regression models are compared using metrics such as the Area Under Curve (AUC), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) such as sensitivity, specificity, and measures of classification. These are all internal model metrics that are produced through assessing how the model fits the test dataset and how well it classifies archaeological site locations given a certain probability cut-point. In addition, the variance, standard error (SE), and coefficient of variation (CoV) are calculated for each metric to assess how stable the results are after reproducing the models over numerous (e.g., 100–1,000) runs of the model with different CV selections and new non-site data samples. The final metric used in model selection is the range of Kg values derived from applying the model to the study area and computing the results. While the previous measures are more specific to a model's stability and performance when predicting across different samples of the test data, the Kg and cross-over graph for each model

demonstrates the model's performance when every cell of the study area is considered. In all of the previous APMs described in Task 1 of this project, the resulting performance measures of the models, when available, were calculated based on a sample of non-sites, typically a sample of a few dozen to a few hundred locations. In this study, the Kg results are calculated based on the full population of cells in the modeled area, typically a sample of tens to hundreds of millions of locations. The result of calculating Kg based on the full population, as opposed to a much smaller non-site sample, is that there may be greater variance between the model's performance on the test data, but lower bias in the end results because all of the data are being considered. Steps within the modeling process such as bootstrapping and K-folds CV, are used to reduce the aforementioned variance.

Based on these metrics, trends in the differences between model types are illustrated. In general, the measures of model accuracy and prediction success increase from the LR to adaptive regression splines to the RF model. Additionally, the Kg statistic and percentage of site-present cells captured in the high or moderate sensitivity classes increase from Model Class 2 through the three regression models. Perhaps more importantly, however, the behavior of each model within a sub-region becomes apparent when these metrics are viewed across the spectrum. For example, one model may achieve a good rating of a metric based on the mean over 1,000 runs, but a high variance to those results will show the model is unstable. Or perhaps a model may only achieve a high metric score from the LR, but the Kg suffers because of the distribution of the probability. In essence, each region, represented by its physiographic character and associated site sample, has a unique identity or behavior that is expressed through the models and can be traced across the various model methods and metrics. The key to selecting the appropriate model or combination of models for each region is to read this behavior, through the metrics and Kg values, and view them in relation to the map and the project objectives.

Upon selecting the model that best represents the modeling regions, the high, moderate, and low sensitivity cut points are established based on Kg and the cross-over graphs, and the raster is reclassified. The reclassified rasters are then merged to compile a full assessment for the study area. The results section below will discuss the specifics of each model and the qualities that led to its selection.

STUDY AREA OVERVIEW AND DATA

The pilot model study area is composed of four counties in central Pennsylvania: Blair, Centre, Clearfield, and Clinton (Figure 10). This region was selected for a number of reasons including its central location, wide range of physiographic and topographic settings that represent much of the state, and a relatively well-documented and up-to-date archaeological site sample. The overall size of the study area, 3,692 square miles, is adequate to give an impression of how to manage large raster datasets, but small enough to be used as a testing ground for different methods. The prehistoric site sample for the four-county area includes 884 prehistoric sites.

PILOT MODEL STUDY AREA ENVIRONMENT

As shown in Figure 11, the four-county pilot model study area is intersected by the five physiographic sections listed in Table 2. The Pittsburgh Low Plateau of the Appalachian Plateaus province is the largest section within the pilot model study area. This is followed by the Appalachian Mountain, Allegheny Front, and Deep Valleys, in that order. The smallest section is the Susquehanna Lowland in the northeast quadrant of the study area. The five physiographic sections were divided into riverine and upland settings to create the 10 separately modeled regions discussed within this report (Figure 12). The 10 regions of the pilot model study area (not to be confused with the 10 statewide Regions presented in the Task 2 report [Harris 2013b]) are as follows: Riverine Region 1 (RR1), Upland Region 1 (UR1), Riverine Region 2 (RR2), Upland Region 2 (UR2), Riverine Region 3 (RR3), Upland Region 3 (UR3), Riverine Region 4 (RR4), Upland Region 4 (UR4), Riverine Region 5 (RR5), and Upland Region 5 (UR5).

Table 2 – Physiographic Provinces and Sections within the Pilot Model Study Area.

Province	Section	Modeling Region
Appalachian Plateaus	Allegheny Front	Region 2
	Deep Valleys	Region 1
	Pittsburgh Low Plateau	Region 4
Ridge and Valley	Appalachian Mountain	Region 5
	Susquehanna Lowland	Region 3

Figure 10 - Location of pilot model study area.

Figure 11 – Physiographic sections of the pilot model study area.

Figure 12 – Modeling regions within the pilot model study area.

Appalachian Plateaus Province

The Appalachian Plateaus province comprises 10 physiographic sections and spatially occupies the land area north and west of the Appalachian Mountains. The 10 sections that constitute this physiographic province include the Northwestern Glaciated Plateau, the High Plateau, the Pittsburgh Low Plateau, the Waynesburg Hills, the Allegheny Mountain section, the Allegheny Front section, the Deep Valleys section, the Glaciated High Plateau section, the Glaciated Low Plateau section, and the Glaciated Pocono Plateau section. As only three of these sections are situated within the pilot model study area, they are the only areas that will be described.

Allegheny Front Section. The Allegheny front section constitutes the eastern boundary of the Appalachian Plateaus Provinces. The topography of the section is dominated by a variety of hills that were created by a combination of fluvial (river/stream) erosion and periglacial mass wasting (freeze/thaw creep, slow flow of soils above the permafrost resulting in phenomena such as landslides, rock fall, etc.). The eastern half of the section is characterized by rounded to linear hills that gradually rise in stepped elevation as they approach an escarpment and the beginning of the Appalachian Mountain section to the east. The boundary is delineated by a stream that runs along the base of the aforesaid escarpment. These hills are crisscrossed by narrow valleys that separate the individual hilltops. These hills often appear stepped as they form escarpments/cliffs as the elevation increases. The effect is that of a series of hilly stairs rising to the east to meet with the Appalachian Mountains. The western half of the section is sloped away to the west in a series of undulating hills. The underlying bedrock throughout this section is dominated by shale, siltstone, and sandstone. The geologic structure of the section is fairly uniform, characterized by beds having a low northwest dip, with the occasional fault making an appearance. The exception to this is in the southernmost portion of the section, which can be differentiated by the transition to geologic structure typified by broad folds. The elevation throughout the section is highly variable, ranging from just 540 feet to as much as 2,980 feet. This variance is due in large part to the undulating land surface and deep-cut valleys between hills and escarpments. The drainage pattern for this area is classified as both parallel and trellis. While the eastern edge of this section is defined by an escarpment, the western edge is largely arbitrary but is loosely delineated by the boundaries of coal fields in areas such as the adjacent Pittsburgh Low Plateau section.

Pittsburgh Low Plateau Section. The Pittsburgh Low Plateau section covers an immense land area located to the west of the Appalachian Mountains and north of the Allegheny Mountains. It continues all the way to the western edge of the state and into Ohio and West Virginia and is defined to the northwest by the southern extreme of glaciation. The dominant topography of the area is variable. Some areas are relatively smooth while other areas are characterized by a more undulating ground surface. Shallow, narrow valleys are littered across the landscape. These small valleys form a dendritic drainage network that is typical of the section. There are many tiny streams joining to form large streams, which in turn join to form larger creeks and rivers, etc.

The topography of the section was created by a combination of fluvial erosion and periglacial mass wasting. It is noteworthy that due to human activity and centuries of mining there are many areas that are composed of strip mines or reclaimed mine land. Human modification of the environment has had an important geologic and topographic impact on the terrain and topography of this section, and is in part what defines it. While the underlying rock contains much of the same sandstone, siltstone, and shale found in the Allegheny Front section, the Pittsburgh Low Plateau also includes the notable additions of limestone and coal. The geologic structure of the section is again variable but in general is typified by moderate to low amplitude open folds (which are responsible for the undulating appearance of the land surface). In the northern portion of the section the appearance of these open folds decrease and the land surface levels out. While the section is as a whole far flatter than the Allegheny Front section, it too ranges in elevation from 600 feet to 2,340 feet.

The Deep Valleys Section. The Deep Valleys section is located to the north of the Allegheny Front section and to the northeast of the Pittsburgh Low Plateau section. It is bounded on the west by the High Plateau section and the east by the Glaciated High Plateau section. Its northern border occurs at the New York state line, although the topography and geology of this section continue north into New York. As its name suggests, the Deep Valleys section is typified by the presence of very deep and angular valleys. While there are some narrow areas of upland between the valleys, the overall impression of the topography of this section is that of sharply cut valleys. The angular nature of the valleys creates an angulate and/or rectangular drainage pattern where streams tend to meet at right angles. This results when water flows between angular breaks in rock formations that have similar densities and erode evenly. In these geologic situations the water is more likely to follow the path of least resistance along established geologic fractures, creating deep, regular valleys. The formation of the valleys in this section are further assisted by the process of fluvial erosion and periglacial mass wasting. The underlying bedrock of the area is composed of sandstone, shale, siltstone, and sedimentary conglomerate. The geologic structure of the section is characterized by moderate-amplitude open folds. These folds are responsible for the directionality of the valleys within the section. The elevations to be found within the section are again quite variable due to the upland/valley dichotomy. As a result elevation ranges from 560 feet to 2,560 feet.

Ridge and Valley Province

The Ridge and Valley province is composed of seven physiographic sections and spatially occupies the land area of the Appalachian Mountains and the adjacent area. The northern extreme of this section occurs at the edge of glaciation whereas the area to the south and east of the province is defined by the beginning of the piedmont. The previously described Appalachian Plateaus province lies to the west. The seven sections that constitute this physiographic province include the Appalachian Mountain section, the Susquehanna Lowland section, the Anthracite

Valley section, the Anthracite Upland section, the Blue Mountain Section, the Great Valley section, and the South Mountain section. As only two of these sections are situated within the pilot model study area they are the only areas that will be described below.

Appalachian Mountain Section. The Appalachian Mountain section is composed of the mountainous region in the middle of the state. It is bordered to the southeast by Blue Mountain, to the northwest by a lowland valley, to the north and west by the extent of the ridge lines, and to the south by the Pennsylvania state border with Maryland. The dominant topographic features are long, narrow ridges separated by valleys of varying width, which are created by the underlying geologic structure of open and closed plunging folds that have narrow hinges and planar limbs and are riddled with faults. Karst features are also common within this section and they occur when a carbonate-based rock-like limestone erodes and dissolves to form voids such as caves and sinkholes. The underlying rock types present in the section are sandstone, siltstone, shale, conglomerate, limestone, and dolomite. Both limestone and dolomite will exhibit the karst features. As the section is typified by steep ridges and valleys, a trellis-type drainage system has developed wherein streams flow the direction of the major valley folds and are fed by small streams running vertically down the steep valley slopes. In some areas a more angulate drainage pattern occurs, but this is dependent on the presence of more erosion resistant rock. Additionally, because of the karst geologic processes, there is a fair amount of underground stream action within the section. The typical geologic processes of fluvial erosion and periglacial mass wasting have contributed to the development of this section, but this region is unique from those previously discussed due to the operation of the karst geologic process, which shapes the bedrock environment by dissolving carbonate rock. As the name of the section suggests, the section is mountainous and thus the elevation is subject to extremes, which in this case range from as little as 440 feet to as much as 2,775 feet.

Susquehanna Lowland Section. The Susquehanna Lowland section is located to the northwest of the Appalachian Mountain section and immediately south of the southern extreme of glaciation. To its southeast lies the Blue Mountain ridge and beyond that the start of the Piedmont Province. The section is typified by low to moderately high linear ridges that are separated by similarly linear valleys. The most notable feature of this landscape is the Susquehanna River valley, which dominates the terrain. Similar to the Appalachian Mountain section, the base geology of this section is composed of open and closed plunging folds that have narrow hinges and planar limbs. It is this base structure that creates the aforementioned linear ridges and valleys. While the same geological structure exists in both the Appalachian Mountain section and the Susquehanna Lowland section, it is a matter of the amplitude of the folds that separates the two, the lowland folds being far less severe. It should be no surprise, therefore, that a similar drainage system has developed in this section as was present in the Appalachian Mountain section. A trellis-type drainage system has developed wherein streams flow the direction of the major valley folds and

are fed by small streams running vertically down valley slopes. As was the case in the Appalachian Mountain section, some areas with more erosion resistant rock have a more angulate drainage pattern. The primary difference between the two sections is the absence of the karst features and the associated geologic process of chemical weathering of carbonate rock. This is not due to the absence of limestone or dolomite bedrock, which are both present along with sandstone, siltstone, shale, and conglomerate. Another key difference between this section and the Appalachian Mountain section lies in the geological processes that formed the area. While this section has undergone fluvial erosion similar to the Appalachian Mountain section, it has also been subjected to glacial erosion and deposition in its northwestern portions, an occurrence not experienced by the Appalachian Mountain section. As the name would suggest, this section is lowland, so its elevations are far restrained in comparison to those of the adjacent Appalachian Mountain and Blue Mountain sections. The elevations within this section ranges from 260 feet to 1,715 feet.

PILOT MODEL STUDY AREA PASS DATA

The pilot model study area included 884 individual prehistoric archaeological sites (Figure 13). According to the data contained in the PASS database, these sites range in age from the Paleoindian through to the Contact-Historic period (Table 3). Roughly half of the sites were documented by artifact collector interview or through unknown methods. Approximately half the sites were documented through systematic methods or field-verified collector accounts (Table 4). The landforms listed for each site in the PASS database are more commonly listed as riverine oriented, such as floodplain, stream bench, or terrace. The less common landforms include slopes and ridgetops (Table 5). Finally, the vast majority of sites are not stratified or the potential for stratification is unknown. Approximately 6.5% of the sites are listed as stratified (Table 6).

Table 3 – Temporal Components of PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

Temporal Component	Count
Prehistoric	840
Archaic	205
Archaic - Late	190
Woodland	174
Woodland - Late	154
Transitional	112
Archaic - Middle	61
Woodland - Middle	38
Archaic - Early	32
Woodland - Early	32
Paleoindian	10
Contact-Historic	1

Figure 13 – Locations of known prehistoric archaeological sites within the pilot model study area.

Table 4 – Site Discovery Methods of PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

Site Discovery Method	Count
Unknown	246
Collector Interview	182
Systematic Surface Survey	147
Systematic Sub-Surface Testing	123
Shovel Testing	87
Collector Interview with Field Check	68
Test Pits	15
Extensive Test Excavation	9
Non-Systematic Surface Survey	7

Table 5 – Topographic Settings of PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

Topographic Setting	Count
Floodplain	423
Stream Bench	147
Terrace	84
Hillslope	54
Hill Ridge/Toe	48
Upland Flat	26
Hilltop	20
Saddle	12
Middle Slopes	11
Rise in Floodplain	10
Lower Slopes	8
Ridgetop	3
Upper Slopes	2

Table 6 – Vertical Stratification PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

Site Vertical Stratification	Count
No	645
Unknown	182
Yes, Top Stratum Visible From Surface	37
Yes	13
Yes, Top Stratum Buried Under Historical Deposits	4
Yes, Top Stratum Buried Under Sterile Deposits	3

A variable within the PASS database that is important to keep in mind for this analysis is how the boundaries of the sites were defined. According to the PASS database, approximately one-third of the sites were defined by the boundaries drawn on the older paper USGS 1:24,000 scale quadrangle maps or, more recently, from aerial photos or larger-scale maps. The other two-thirds of sites are listed as “GIS Point Buffer” (Table 7). These sites are defined by a buffer of an arbitrary dimension because the true extent of the site is unknown. The arbitrary radius of these sites is typically 28 or 40 m. Finally, regarding National Register eligibility, the vast majority of PASS sites in the pilot model study area have not yet been evaluated (Table 8). Approximately 2.5% of the known sites are considered eligible by the State Historic Preservation Office.

Table 7 – Basis for Boundary Definition of PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

Boundary Source	Count
GIS Point Buffer	504
Quad Sheet	294

Table 8 – National Register Eligibility for PASS Sites within Pilot Study Area

National Register Status	Count
Insufficient Information to Evaluate	782
Demolished or 100% Destroyed	52
SHPO: Not Eligible	28
SHPO: Eligible	22

PILOT MODEL FINDINGS

The pilot model study had two main objectives: 1) construct a workflow that incorporates valid data preparation, modeling, validation, and GIS methodologies that is scalable, repeatable, and applicable to the remainder of Pennsylvania; and 2) through this workflow, create assessments of prehistoric archaeological site sensitivity that are balanced toward minimizing false-negative errors while allowing for a moderate false-positive rate—both commensurate with the quality of the site data in the modeled region. The following section on findings will address each of these goals separately for the sake of organization, but achieving both goals is necessary for these models to succeed.

WORKFLOW AND CONSTRAINTS

The previous Modeling Approach section presents an outline of the process that resulted from this pilot study. The workflow developed through this project has three primary constraints: 1) the use of proven modeling and statistical techniques that are applicable to the mission of this project and compatible with archaeological theory and data quality; 2) the ability to address the unique character of archaeological site location data and settlement patterns; and 3) the flexibility to handle massive datasets requiring intense computation.

Statistical Methods

The development of statistical methods for data preparation, model creation, and validation began with the background study presented in Task 1 (Harris 2013a). The intent of Task 1 was to document the types of procedures used in APMs within Pennsylvania, analyze their methods, and evaluate their findings and validity. From this, a number of different modeling approaches were chronicled and the benefits and drawbacks of each were explored. This understanding was coupled with a thorough background in worldwide APM literature to form the framework of the proposed approach.

Models from each of the three model classes employed in this project were documented for Pennsylvania in the Task 1 background study. The basic judgmentally weighted model type (Model Class 1) was used with some success by Neusius and Neusius (1989) within the Crooked Creek drainage. Proportionally weighting methods (Model Class 2) were used by Glenn (2010) and Whitley and Bastianini (1992). Glenn used a relatively simple proportional weighting scheme for the Erie National Wildlife Refuge, whereas Whitley and Bastianini developed a more intricate method that added penalty weights for background values that carried low site proportions. The results from each author were variable and not extensively well reported, but

showed promise. Finally, a well performed LR model (Model Class 3) was documented by Hart (1994) for the Lake Erie Plain and Glacial Escarpment area of northwestern Pennsylvania. Hart used statistical tests to determine each predictor's ability to discriminate site locations from the background and a stepwise LR to model probabilities of site occurrence. Hart's methods and documentation were the most sophisticated and rigorous example documented within the Task 1 report and most closely adhered to methods established in the canonical APM text, *Quantifying the Present and Predicting the Past: Theory, Method, and Application of Archaeological Predictive Modeling* (Judge and Sebastian 1988).

Additional elements of the rigorous methods developed in Judge and Sebastian (1988) were present in a number of the studies reviewed in Task 1, such as LR as attempted by Duncan et al. (1999). Few aside from Hart (1994), however, put together a standard program based on the elements of data preparation, model selection, parameterization, validation, and detailed reporting. The workflow developed for the pilot model attempts to incorporate all of the important findings of the era of APM that led to Judge and Sebastian (1988) and build from that point with more recent research within APM and modern statistical techniques used in fields outside of archaeology. While a scant few publications dedicated to APM have made a notable impact since Judge and Sebastian (1988), more recent work by Philip Verhagen and his colleagues from Leiden University, the Netherlands, has made significant contributions. Publications such as Kamermans et al. (2009), Verhagen (2009), and Verhagen and Whitley (2012) broke through with a more current assessment of APM expectations and the development of statistical model testing and validation methods. In some cases, the methods were a refresh of those presented in Judge and Sebastian (1988), but a number of new approaches were recommended. The use of resampling methods such as bootstrapping and CV were advocated in these works to better assess model predictability and stability. Additionally, the use of validation techniques using presence/absence contingency tables (referred to as a "confusion matrix" in many fields) were offered as appropriate methods to understanding and communicating the ability of a model to predict site locations. While Kamermans, Verhagen, and much of the more recent literature do suggest alternative statistical models and model classes that could benefit APM, they focus more of their energy on understanding what APM has to offer and how to be more rigorous in testing and validation (an exception to this is Whitley's development of Causality-Based Cognitive models [Whitley 2005]). The pilot model utilizes the testing and validation recommendations made by these more recent publications.

The statistical study of the first implementation of the Minnesota state-wide archaeological predictive model (Mn Model) by Oehlert and Shea (2007) offers a host of new models and measures that can be implemented within the framework of APM. As a non-archaeologist statistician, Oehlert's perspective on the methods and results of the Mn Model is welcome and refreshing. From a statistical point of view, informed on the unique constraints of archaeological

data, Oehlert and Shea offer a number of up-to-date approaches that are used broadly and successfully for predictive analytics outside of archaeology. These approaches include modeling methods such as CART, Naïve Bayes, Bootstrap Aggregating (Bagging and Boosting), and the utilization of the confusion matrix (presence/absence contingency table) to derive model validity metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, Positive Predictive Gain (PPG), and the ROC curve. While conceptually the approaches of the models and metrics discussed by Oehlert and Shea are not foreign to archaeology, the field has not to this point incorporated these developments. Research in ecology, biology, geomorphology, machine learning, genetics, and data analytics have advanced these techniques, and these disciplines have deep catalogs of research and application. Many of the problems to which these methods are applied are not dissimilar to those faced in archaeology and can be adapted to fit our theoretical frameworks and datasets. The creation of the unified and rigorous approach undertaken in the pilot model study relied as heavily on developments outside of archaeology as those within. The previously mentioned studies by Felicísimo and Gómez-Muñoz (2007), Felicísimo et al. (2012), Leathwick and Hastie (2006), and Märker and Heydari-Guran (2009) strongly influence the methods of the pilot model. Finally, the recommendations offered by Oehlert and Shea (2007) are used as an invaluable opportunity to learn from the many trials and errors from the Mn Model project.

Application to Archaeological Data

One of the most glaring issues confronting the successful modeling of archaeological data using environmental variables is the uncertainty posed by human agency and culture. While we cannot hope to decode the collective thought processes of people occupying the earth millennia ago, the locations at which they discarded material remains do provide the scant clues we need to search for a pattern. As discussed earlier in this report, this source of uncertainty is acknowledged in this study and its findings. The methods employed in this project seek to approximate only the environmental constraints that helped guide site location decisions and rely on the fact that sites are distributed non-randomly in respect to measurable environmental factors, a proposition expanded on by Kvamme (1988:327). The more practical and addressable constraint of archaeological data is that archaeological sites are an exceedingly rare event. In the pilot model, documented archaeological sites compose 0.087% of the study area. This imbalance between site-presence and site-absence leads to difficulties in modeling accuracy and estimating error. Model accuracy is affected by the weighting applied by statistical models to the massive site-absence class (King and Zeng 2001). Estimating classification error is affected by the site-absence class's influence on measures such as the false positive rate (FPR), prevalence, and detection rate (Doswell et al. 1990). Each of these issues can be addressed, however, through adjustments in methods and interpretation.

In modeling and forecasting, a “rare event” can be thought of as an event that occurs about 0.1% to 1% of the time. This concept is applicable to modeling instances such as disease prevalence,

rare weather events, manufacturing defects, credit card fraud, or environmental catastrophes. As with archaeological sites, the norm with these events is that nothing happens. Modeling such rare events raises the issues of bias and interpretation because models are often lazy in that they optimize for 99% of the non-event cases. In addition to the theoretical concerns discussed earlier, the imbalance presented by the norm of site-absence versus the rare case of site-presence is the most pressing issue in dealing with archaeological site data. Fortunately, there are methods to deal with this.

The two primary ways to address rare event data are to handle it in the model end by parameterization and weighting, or to handle it in the data end by resampling data to address the imbalance (Chen et al. 2004). In the pilot model, the latter approach was used to mitigate the effects of rare events. The primary mitigation of rare events employed in this process is to minimize the effects by making the event of site presence less rare. This measure is used in two different ways in this workflow: first sites are made less rare by considering every 10×10 -m cell within a site as a site-present observation. In total there are 884 individual sites within the pilot model area, but these sites encompass 74,387 site-present cells. Aside from the clear advantages to measuring environmental predictors on a cell basis instead of an aggregate site basis, this approach has the added benefit of minimizing the effects of the rare event. Although site-present cells still only compose 0.087% of the study area, the larger the number of rare events, the less impact they have on the analysis. For instance, the bias associated with a data sample of 10 events out of 100 non-events is greater than 10,000 events out of 100,000 non-events even though the prevalence is the same: 10%.

The second approach to addressing this imbalance is resampling through bootstrapping and CV. CV is the method by which a sample of observations is split into a number of different but equal-sized classes. The number of classes is referred to as K and the classes themselves are referred to as folds, which is why it is called K -folds CV. After splitting the data into roughly equal sized folds, the model is computed using a training set of $K-1$ folds (or 9 of the 10 folds if $K = 10$), and tested with the remaining fold. Metrics are computed on the predictions made for the out-of-sample (OOS) fold data and the process is repeated using the test data as part of the training set and a new fold as the test data. This is repeated K times. In this way, the predictions are always tested on data that are independent of the data on which the model was trained. This is a standard method in modeling (Kohavi 1995) and advocated for in APM (Verhagan 2009). Additionally, some models such as RF incorporate internal CV methods. To further develop the unbiased estimate of model validity and reduce the effects of unbalanced classes, this approach uses bootstrapping to allow for creation of different CV folds and perturbations of the non-site sample. Bootstrapping in this project is utilized in the form of resampling the background cells from the background cell population with replacement (i.e., incorporating all previously sampled cells back into the population to obtain a new, independent sample). After a full round of K -folds

CV, the site-absent sample is resampled to create a new site-absent set that is equal in size to the site-present set and the CV is repeated with new folds. This bootstrap is repeated from 5 to 100 times depending on the model type and application. In essence, this approach uses a randomized and significant portion of the site-absent dataset to build hundreds of models that are then tested against independent test samples. For each model, the test metrics are recorded, and finally the means and coefficients of variations are computed to estimate model validity and stability across the data space.

Finally, the imbalance of classes and effects of the rare event need to be considered in the interpretation of model results and the confusion matrix. Many measures of the confusion matrix rely on a reasonable balance between observed presence and absence in order to be of interpretive value. For example, positive and negative predictive values, precision, F-measure, and false-positive rate are highly dependent on a reasonable balance. Other measures such as positive and negative prediction gain, accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity are less dependent on such a balance. When interpreting a confusion matrix, the balance of the site-present and site-absent classes should be understood prior to using the resulting metrics. Throughout this report, attempts will be made to point out metrics that may be skewed by unbalanced classes.

Data Handling

The ability to handle and manipulate massive datasets is the final constraint discussed here. This constraint is perhaps the most important of the project, yet the least exciting. Without the ability to efficiently manage terabytes of data for each model region, the mitigation measures of CV and bootstrapping and the processor-intensive statistical models would not be possible.

Simply, the primary factor in managing this issue is time. Fortunately, computers do not follow a 9–5 schedule and may be put to work at all hours of day and night. The script-based approach taken to this project allows for the execution of models and predictions throughout the night and over weekends. For many of the bootstrapped CV methods, 5–25 hours of processing time are required. Of course, the hardware on which these processes execute is very important. The pilot model was built on three 64-bit work stations with a total of 20 cores and ranging in RAM from 8 to 25 gigabytes. Numerous external USB 3.0 hard drives of 2 terabytes were used to store the base data and all forms of manipulated data. Server-based data backups with nightly off-site replication were used for data redundancy and security.

On the software side, large datasets were handled through scripting, parallelization, routine optimization, and data chunking. As mentioned, the modeling workflow in this project is implemented through the use of scripting. The R statistical language and the Python language were used to formalize each step of the model development process into repeatable and reproducible code. In addition to gains in process efficiency, this approach allows for

standardization and reproducibility of the methods for the remainder of the project and for the future. Additionally, where appropriate, highly parallel procedures such as random sampling and data resampling were programmed to execute in parallel and use multiple cores. Finally, programming routines were optimized using the most appropriate functions and through vectorization where available. Vectorization is a feature of some programming languages that allows for functions to be executed on entire vectors (strings of values) at once, as opposed to individual values. Each of these methods, in conjunction with capable hardware, are what allow for the handling of large datasets and statistically valid handling of this rare-event data.

MODEL TYPES AND MODEL FIT

Throughout the pilot model process, a great deal was learned about how well each of the model types works when compared to one another. As previously discussed, the use of LR in APM has a relatively long history and there are many examples of its capabilities. The same can be said for judgmentally and proportionally weighted models, but evaluating them outside of the context in which they are applied is more difficult than with the statistical models. On the other hand, the model types of adaptive regression splines and tree-based methods such as RF have few if any published applications within archaeology. The pilot model was an opportunity to test these models and compare their predictive ability and limitations against the baseline of the LR. Overall, where data quality was adequate, the adaptive regression splines method worked better than LR, and the RF was the most accurate. Note that being more accurate and being the better model are two different things, as will be discussed later. These results are not too surprising given the literature available on these techniques. The following section will give greater detail on each model type's ability to predict the sensitivity for prehistoric archaeological site locations within the pilot model study area.

Model Class 1 – Judgmental Weighting

For areas lacking archaeological site data where only Model Class 1 was used, it is difficult to evaluate model performance. Not only are there few if any sites to assess model fit, but these models, being composed of combinations of weighting schemes, are simplistic by design and intended to be interpreted as such. It would be possible to apply a more complex statistical model to a region with little to no data, but the interpretation of the model would suffer because the predictors and coefficients would have been based on a different, data-rich region. Statistically comparing the environments of the data-rich and data-poor regions could mitigate some of this effect, however. The judgmental model is meant to incorporate the uncertainty of the poor quality dataset and make conservative assessments of sensitivity. With this conservative assessment will come a high Kg. One approach to understanding the validity of the different weighting schemes of Model Class 1 is to test them against all of the sites within the pilot model region (Table 9).

Table 9 - Model Class 1 Model Performance Metrics for Entire Pilot Model Site Sample

Slope Scheme	Distance to Water Scheme	Model Number	Mean Site %	Mean Kg	K-S D-value	K-S p-value
4	3	model 18	86.33%	0.6487	0.6000	0.0546
3	3	model 13	86.33%	0.6482	0.6000	0.0546
3	2	model 12	69.59%	0.7346	0.7222	0.0002
4	2	model 17	69.59%	0.7344	0.7222	0.0002
2	1	model 6	64.49%	0.7728	0.7222	0.0002
1	1	model 1	62.40%	0.7804	0.7000	0.0001
3	5	model 15	61.70%	0.7168	0.7059	0.0004
4	5	model 20	61.70%	0.7139	0.7059	0.0004
1	4	model 4	60.67%	0.7468	0.6471	0.0016
5	1	model 21	60.52%	0.6975	0.6842	0.0003
1	2	model 2	59.51%	0.7811	0.6667	0.0007
3	1	model 11	58.43%	0.7638	0.6316	0.0010
4	1	model 16	58.43%	0.7582	0.6316	0.0010
2	2	model 7	58.15%	0.7861	0.6316	0.0010
5	4	model 24	57.31%	0.5977	0.6111	0.0024
5	5	model 25	53.70%	0.6255	0.5789	0.0034
5	2	model 22	53.15%	0.7463	0.5556	0.0077
5	3	model 23	52.11%	0.7413	0.5556	0.0077
1	3	model 3	52.49%	0.8154	0.6111	0.0024
2	5	model 10	50.99%	0.8035	0.5000	0.0135
2	4	model 9	48.70%	0.7984	0.5500	0.0047
4	4	model 19	48.70%	0.7434	0.5714	0.0021
3	4	model 14	48.70%	0.7428	0.5714	0.0021
2	3	model 8	48.60%	0.8098	0.5500	0.0047
1	5	model 5	47.05%	0.8100	0.5263	0.0104

Note: The weight schemes in the first two columns are listed in Table 1; Mean Site % and Mean Kg are means of the top five summed sensitivity values; K-S statistic is the D-value from the K-S test.

As shown in Table 9, the various weighting scheme combinations led to a range of fits. This table is sorted first by Mean Site % and then by Mean Kg. For each of the 25 model runs, the percent of site-present cells and background cells is calculated for each summed sensitivity value and the Kg is derived. The mean of the site-present percentages and Kg values for each model are shown in Mean Site % and Mean Kg columns. These columns give us a way to evaluate the utility of each model. Further, the D-value of the K-S test is included along with its p-value. For the K-S test, the closer the D-value is to 1, the more different the distributions of site-present and

background cells. The p-value gives the significance of the difference. The highest performing weighting scheme appears to be from models 18 and 13; models 12, 17, 6, and 1 are also worthwhile models. Models 18 and 13 are very similar in the weighting scheme and results. Each model captures approximately 85% of the known sites within the upper end of the sensitivity values, and does so with a Kg of ~0.65. The K-S D- and p-values for models 18 and 13 are not as good as for the models that follow, but they do suggest an acceptable difference in the shape of the distributions. By referencing Table 1 (in the Modeling Approach section of this report), it is learned that the weighting schemes of models 13 and 18 assign relatively even decreases in weight as distance from water resources and slope increases. Model 18 uses a slightly more aggressive weighting scheme for slope. Interestingly, as a very general observation, the more aggressive weighting schemes for distance to water and more even schemes for slope are more common in the more successful models.

The results presented in Table 9 indicate that there are a handful of models, led by models 18 and 13, that could be applied uniformly to the entire project area and produce adequate quantitative results. The drawbacks of this approach are that there may be more predictors that can tailor the models for more effective assessments and that different samples of sites within the study area may prefer one combination of weights that differs from the site sample as a whole, as will be discussed further on. Further, the ability to derive unbiased prediction errors and performance metrics is not possible with this type of simple model. The benefit of this model is that it does not require known site locations and its interpretation is very straightforward.

Model Class 2 – Proportionally Weighted

The proportionally weighted models created for the pilot study more accurately describe the locations of archaeological sites within each region, but require sufficient data in order to determine correlations. In this model type, statistical tests are performed to compare the measures of a possible predictor variable at site locations and the background environment. In total, the full site-present cell sample from each region is statistically compared to a randomly sampled set of 50,000 background values; this process is repeated 100 times for new randomly selected sets of 50,000 background values.

Two statistical tests are used in this process; the K-S test and the MW U test (a two-sample Wilcoxon rank-sum test). As described earlier in this report, each of these tests compare the distributions of predictor measures at site-present versus background locations and report two values: the test statistic measures the difference in distribution shape and a p-value assesses the significance of the difference. This battery of testing is repeated for each region and for each of the 70 possible predictor variables. A predictor of randomly assigned numbers is also included in the testing to give a baseline from which to interpret the results.

Tables 10–17 give the results of the K-S test and MW U test. Each table represents the three to five predictor variables that were selected from the total of 70 to represent the archaeological sites of each region containing 10 or more sites. The codes that represent each predictor are provided in Appendix B. Also included in each table is the resulting statistics from the random variable. The selection of suitable predictors was based on both the test statistic results and type of variable that the predictor represents. The columns labeled “Mean D” are the D-values from the K-S test averaged over the 100 repetitions of the test using new randomly selected background samples. This value ranges from 1 to 0, with 1 signifying very different distributions, and 0 signifying equal distributions. Similarly, the “Mean U” column is the U-value from the MW U test. The U-value can range from 0 to a non-specified upper limit that depends on the sample size (half the product of the number of values in each group). With the large samples used here, the U-value can be quite large. These two statistical tests compare distributions in different ways, and the resulting values give complementary interpretations. The D-value gives a more absolute assessment of the difference, while the U-value, in this case, signals the directionality of the difference by how far it is from a central value approximated by the random variable. The magnitude of this property is dependent upon the sample size of known sites. Given these results, predictors with the highest D- and more extreme U-value, along with small p-values, are interpreted as the best at discriminating site-present locations from the background environment.

Table 10 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Riverine Region 1

Riverine Region 1 (n=13,711 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
tpi_10c	0.592	p < 0.0001	630617689	p < 0.0001
ed_hydro_2	0.555	p < 0.0001	611397900	p < 0.0001
std_16c	0.516	p < 0.0001	139820998	p < 0.0001
slpvr_16c	0.486	p < 0.0001	149118233	p < 0.0001
costdist_3	0.400	p < 0.0001	159364835	p < 0.0001
random	0.016	p = 0.0165	367681897	p = 0.1333

Table 11 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Riverine Region 2

Riverine Region 2 (n=5,783 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
rng_4c	0.500	p < 0.0001	70757950	p < 0.0001
costdist_4	0.438	p < 0.0001	96549585	p < 0.0001
ed_hydro_3	0.423	p < 0.0001	236544498	p < 0.0001
random	0.011	p = 0.568	154106395	p = 0.4443

Table 12 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Riverine Region 3

Riverine Region 3 (n=8,005 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
ed_hydro_6	0.420	p < 0.0001	142038302	p < 0.0001
tpi_sd10c	0.377	p < 0.0001	297887533	p < 0.0001
ed_hydro_5	0.365	p < 0.0001	159818382	p < 0.0001
eldrop27c	0.265	p < 0.0001	288112118	p < 0.0001
random	0.014	p = 0.1575	214592932	p = 0.2450

Table 13 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Riverine Region 4

Riverine Region 4 (n=6,472 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
ed_hydro_6	0.627	p < 0.0001	66443784	p < 0.0001
elev_2_drainh	0.426	p < 0.0001	107194150	p < 0.0001
rng_8c	0.394	p < 0.0001	97414401	p < 0.0001
tpi_10c	0.351	p < 0.0001	244275900	p < 0.0001
random	0.010	p = 0.5687	180540579	p = 0.3237

Table 14 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Riverine Region 5

Riverine Region 5 (n=22,049 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
costdist_4	0.312	p < 0.0001	386819313	p < 0.0001
est_alo_dranh	0.232	p < 0.0001	718457860	p < 0.0001
rng_8c	0.210	p < 0.0001	473212111	p < 0.0001
random	0.008	p = 0.3212	604063571	p = 0.4513

Table 15 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Upland Region 2

Upland Region 2 (n=757 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
ed_hydro_6	0.444	p < 0.0001	11418610	p < 0.0001
costdist_3	0.367	p < 0.0001	15074767	p < 0.0001
elev_2_conf	0.350	p < 0.0001	12235689	p < 0.0001
aspect	0.300	p < 0.0001	14883104	p < 0.0001
tpi_sd50c	0.260	p < 0.0001	15773415	p < 0.0001
random	0.031	p = 0.4691	18958539	p = 0.8776

Table 16 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Upland Region 4

Upland Region 4 (n=3,156 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
cst_alo_dranh	0.489	p < 0.0001	122946923	p < 0.0001
ed_hydro_5	0.475	p < 0.0001	39667786	p < 0.0001
tpi_50c	0.398	p < 0.0001	116721397	p < 0.0001
ed_conflu	0.308	p < 0.0001	103691571	p < 0.0001
random	0.019	p = 0.2410	80129345	p = 0.1421

Table 17 - K-S and MW Statistics for Selected Predictors in Upland Region 5

Upland Region 5 (n=10,370 site-present cells)				
Predictor	Mean D	Mean KS p	Mean U	Mean MW p
costdist_5	0.519	p < 0.0001	121502313	p < 0.0001
slpvr_32c	0.500	p < 0.0001	99356824	p < 0.0001
rng_8c	0.477	p < 0.0001	91683857	p < 0.0001
ed_conflu	0.440	p < 0.0001	376508651	p < 0.0001
random	0.008	p = 0.6292	262302205	p = 0.2792

The selection of predictors depends not only on the magnitude and significance of the statistical tests, but also depends on what the predictor represents. For example, in many upland regions, the variable of elevation proves to be highly significant, but as a predictor this variable is highly biased by where known sites happen to have been discovered. Of course this bias is present in any predictor because of the non-systematic sampling of known site locations, but in choosing representative predictors efforts were made to limit this bias. These efforts include understanding the way each predictor is influenced by the specific distribution of known sites across the landscape within each region and how bias may be expressed. Additionally, many of the predictors represent the same environmental phenomenon, but measured on a different scale. For example, Topographic Position Index (TPI) is measured using neighborhood sizes of 3, 5, 8, 10, 16, and 32 grid cells (with each grid cell being approximately 10 × 10 m). If TPI is a highly discriminant variable for a region it may be highly discriminant at more than one neighborhood size (e.g., tpi_8c and tpi_10c). It would not be useful, however, to include both TPI predictors in any future models because they measure the same phenomenon. In this situation the similar predictors are described as being collinear. Additionally, different predictors can be considered within the same class as they measure the same phenomenon but in different ways. For example, standard deviation of elevation in a given neighborhood (STD) and the range of elevation in a given neighborhood (RNG) are similar measures of topography and are therefore collinear. The selection of predictors for each region was careful to avoid choosing variables that represented the measurement of similar attributes.

The utilization of the selected discriminant predictors for deriving site proportions and weights is discussed in the Modeling Approach section above. The intention of this model is to define the pattern of site location relative to the selected potential predictors and then re-weight the predictors to accentuate the pattern. The summing of the weighted predictor variables assumes that the most sensitive location for archaeological sites is where the most “desirable” portions of the individual predictors intersect. For example, if the most sites are found 10–50 m from streams, between 30 and 50 m in elevation, and on 1–3% slopes, then the most archaeologically sensitive areas are where those three “environments” occur together. This assumes that site location attractiveness, from an environmental standpoint, is an additive property, not a synergism of the attractive combined with seemingly unattractive qualities. Clearly, it is all but assured that the attractiveness of a site location is more than additive, but reducing the site selection process to a more simple form is what allows us to construct these models. This notion and additional discussion about the additive properties of the proportionally weighted model from a mathematical point of view are discussed in the Task 1 report of this project (Harris 2013a).

Where this model is most useful is in regions with lower data quality or with a site sample that has no easily defined pattern relative to the landscape. Typically, in these regions, the data quality is too poor and sparse to achieve stable statistical models, yet there is enough data to define some pattern. The overall ability of the model to classify site locations can be summarized into a confusion matrix, and the K_g and other metrics can be calculated. Model stability, internal classification errors, and other such metrics cannot be calculated, however. In regions with data quality ample enough to define a reliable pattern, models from the statistical category are more likely to be useful.

Model Class 3 – Statistical Models: LR, Adaptive Regression Splines, Tree-Based Methods

Within Model Class 1 we guessed at what might make a suitable landform for human use and projected it across the landscape with little to no validation until we compared it against the known site sample. In Model Class 2, we derived clues about what makes a landform suitable by testing how well it discriminated the full set of known sites in a single region versus the background of the same region. The pattern inferred from how the number of site-present cells was proportionally distributed within these predictors was then uncritically applied to that specific region with little to no assessment of how each individual site was represented by the pattern of all the sites. When more complete data are available this is a better approach than Model Class 1, but it still does not consider each site-present cell and how it interacts with the selected predictors. For this reason, the pilot model project incorporates statistical models (Model Class 3) to seek a more accurate description of the relationship between site locations

and predictors. Also, these models provide much more in-depth metrics that allow for the assessment of model stability and utility.

The approach used in the application of statistical models can be referred to as “Supervised Learning.” While this term originated in the field of machine learning, the principles are applicable to a number of predictive statistical techniques. The term “supervised” refers to the process by which we tell the algorithm what a site-present landform looks like relative to the predictor variables. As an analogy, this is similar to a parent supervising a child to teach them what a house or a car looks like and why they are different. The “learning” component of the term refers to the ability of the model to understand the pattern that makes a site-present location different from a background or non-site location. This understanding is then applied to a testing set of data and the ability to correctly classify a site from a non-site is evaluated. Following the analogy, the child is then shown a number of pictures and asked to say whether each is a car or a house. The child’s ability to correctly distinguish these two forms is a measure of how well they learned or whether they need to be retaught.

The basic approach to teaching the models is to establish the potential predictors, divide the known data into training and testing samples, understand the form of the underlying relationship, teach the algorithm on the training data, test on the testing data, and evaluate the results. In the most general sense, the model takes on the form of:

$$Y = f(X) + \epsilon$$

Where Y is the presence or absence of a site (coded as 1 or 0), $f(X)$ is the function of the predictor X or $X = (x_1, x_2 \dots x_p)$ and ϵ is the error term epsilon. The function f uses the predictor or predictors of X to approximate (predict) what Y should be given X and the error. This takes the form of $P = (Y|X)$ where P is the conditional probability of Y given X . When the function of $f(X)$ is used to predict Y , the resulting approximation is called \hat{Y} , or y-hat (because the circumflex looks like a hat on the Y). So, to implement this approach, we need to find predictors (X) that are useful in determining whether Y is present or absent (1 or 0) and we need to find a function (\hat{f}) that is capable of representing the structure underlying the relationship between X and Y . Finally, we need to recognize the error terms that account for the difference between Y and \hat{Y} .

In the pilot model, the predictors used in the statistical models were the same variables used in Model Class 2 and listed in Tables 10–17. Including additional variables in the statistical models does not have the same drawbacks as in Model Class 2, as many statistical models have mechanisms for variable selection, but for the pilot model only the most discriminant variables were used. Three different functions were chosen to approximate site presence and absence given the predictors: LR, adaptive regression splines (Earth), and a perturbed tree-based ensemble

called RF. The error term for these functions comes in two varieties, the reducible and the irreducible. The reducible errors are exposed through the modeling process, optimized statistically within the models, and minimized through the adjustment of model parameters to find the most appropriate fit. The irreducible errors cannot be addressed through parameterization and must be incorporated in our understanding of the model outcome. These include, but are not limited to, the influence of the cultural component and agency within the environmental expression of site selection (cultural entropy), measurement errors in X and Y , and random components derived from the environment.

The process by which these statistical models fit into a workflow of K-folds CV, bootstrapping, testing, and selection are discussed in the Modeling Approach section of this report. The results of those methods are presented here in the form of model fit, stability, and internal prediction errors. When each model produces comparable metrics they will be included in the same table. Other times they will be tabulated separately, because some metrics are not applicable to all model types.

Logistic Regression (LR). The first kind of model to be applied to the eight regions that contained 10 or more known prehistoric archaeological sites was a LR. This model is a form of the GLM family of non-parametric regression models and uses the logit function to linearize the non-linear relationship between the dichotomous response variable of site presence/absence and the predictors. An initial assessment of this model is done by understanding the significance and contribution of each of the predictor variables. This is done by performing an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test on the regression model to estimate how much variance is accounted for by the addition of each predictor: a p-value derived from the chi-squared distribution assesses the significance. Simply, the greater the portion of the model deviance accounted for by a single predictor, the more important the predictor is to the model. Tables 18–25 show the amount of deviance accounted for by each predictor within each region (ANOVA Dev.), the significance of that predictor’s contribution to the model (ANOVA p), and the estimated coefficient of that predictor (as a log odds). The values in these tables are means derived from a 10-fold CV repeated 500 times with bootstrapped background sample of a size equal to the number of site-present cells. By viewing these tables, it is evident that the selected predictors all have significant contributions to the model, with the exception of tpi_sd50c in the model for Upland Region 2.

Table 18 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Riverine Region 1

LR RR1, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.7177
costdist_3	7329.4825	p < 0.0001	-0.0003
ed_hydro_2	3742.9905	p < 0.0001	0.0074
slpvr_16c	2157.4766	p < 0.0001	-0.0254
std_16c	197.1984	p < 0.0001	0.1465
tpi_10c	2214.4746	p < 0.0001	0.2619

Table 19 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Riverine Region 2

LR RR2, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	-0.2654
costdist_4	2471.489	p < 0.0001	-0.0005
ed_hydro_3	2543.1409	p < 0.0001	0.0012
rng_4c	145.1314	p < 0.0001	0.0433
tri_4c	115.1687	p < 0.0001	-0.0657

Table 20 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Riverine Region 3

LR RR3, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.9066
ed_hydro_5	1987.4074	p < 0.0001	0.0034
ed_hydro_6	951.0733	p < 0.0001	-0.0069
eldrop27c	609.5998	p < 0.0001	0.0206
tpi_sd10c	1419.1277	p < 0.0001	0.0534

Table 21 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Riverine Region 4

LR RR4, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.0350
ed_hydro_6	4209.0098	p < 0.0001	-0.0005
elev_2_drainh	245.8391	p < 0.0001	-0.0232
rng_8c	736.7483	p < 0.0001	-0.0455
tpi_10c	891.6783	p < 0.0001	0.1674

Table 22 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Riverine Region 5

LR RR5, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.6917
costdist_4	4693.5843	p < 0.0001	-0.0004
cst alo dranh	673.7481	p < 0.0001	0.0158
rng_8c	101.8048	p < 0.0001	-0.0195

Table 23 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Upland Region 2

LR UR2, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	2.74
aspect	55.657939	p < 0.0001	-0.00405
costdist_3	94.501093	p < 0.0001	-0.00006
ed hydro_6	68.946853	p < 0.0001	-0.00011
elev_2_conf	33.383373	p < 0.0001	-0.0102
tpi_sd50c	4.312189	p < 0.10	0.00159

Table 24 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Upland Region 4

LR UR4, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.0584
cst alo dranh	1349.0946	p < 0.0001	0.0225
ed_conflu	139.5468	p < 0.0001	0.0004
ed hydro_5	640.7317	p < 0.0001	-0.0023
tpi_50c	118.811	p < 0.0001	0.0182

Table 25 - Deviation and Coefficient Approximation for LR - Upland Region 5

LR UR5, n=500, K=10			
variable	ANOVA Dev.	ANOVA p	β Coefficient
Intersect	n/a	n/a	0.4884
costdist_5	5799.49688	p < 0.0001	-0.0002
ed_conflu	3041.99673	p < 0.0001	0.0011
rng_8c	326.29528	p < 0.0001	-0.0314
slpvr_32c	23.63327	p = 0.0001	-0.0116

With the more well-known form of linear regression, a straight line is fit through the predictor variable values in a way that minimizes the errors between the line and the observed points (sum of squared errors [SSE])—an approach known as the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). The LR function cannot use OLS, however, because the influence of errors is not distributed evenly across the function. For this reason, LR must use an alternated loss function termed the Maximum Likelihood Estimate (MLE). The MLE seeks to fit the model by maximizing the probability (likelihood) that the estimates fit the observations. Because LR does not use the OLS to optimize the model, traditional measures such as R-squared (R^2) and SSE are not applicable. For LR, the primary metric to assess model fit is the Likelihood Ratio Test. The likelihood ratio is simply the difference in model deviance between the null model and the saturated model. In general terms, the null model refers to a regression that only contains the response variable; that is, there are no predictor variables. Figure 14 illustrates the difference between the null model and a saturated model using the same data (the regression in this case is a linear one, but the concept is the same for LR). In the null model, the response variable (y) is predicted based only on the y itself. Given that there is no additional variable to predict what y may be, the average value of y is used. The average value of y in the null model equals the y -intercept, the value on the y -axis where the regression line crosses it (3.217 on Figure 14). The result of the null model is a baseline from which to compare the saturated model (that is, the model that uses additional information in the form of predictor variables). Assuming the chosen predictors are at all appropriate, the fit for the saturated model with predictors should be significantly higher than the null model with no predictors. For LR models the likelihood ratio test compares the outcome of the null and saturated models based on the amount of deviance explained by each model. Presumably the likelihood ratio, the ratio between the null deviance and residual deviance, would become larger as the amount of deviation explained by the predictors increases. The significance of the likelihood ratio is compared to the chi-squared distribution using the difference in degrees-of-freedom between the two models resulting in a p -value. Table 26 shows the likelihood ratio and p -value for each region averaged over 500 repetitions of 10-fold CV. The column labeled “likelihood-ratio CoV” gives the CoV for all of the individual model run likelihood ratios. The CoV is the ratio of the standard deviation (SD) to the mean expressed as a percent. This allows for comparison between models since the magnitude of the likelihood ratio changes based on the number of site-present cells in each region and therefore the magnitude of the SD would flux accordingly. The greater the CoV value, the greater the range of likelihood ratios between model runs, an indication of model instability.

Figure 14 - Schematic of null vs. saturated model applied to same data.

The second measure listed in Table 26 is the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). This is a measure of information loss that is derived from the ratio of model fit versus a penalty for model complexity. Most commonly, the AIC is used to compare two or more candidate models of the same data because the resulting value of AIC depends on the specific model. For this reason, the AIC is not presented here to compare one region to another, but instead to derive the “AIC CoV” and assess how it varies between 5,000 model runs in each region. As with the likelihood CoV, the greater the AIC CoV value, the less stable the model. The magnitude of both CoV values tracked pretty closely, but not exactly since they measure different aspects of model fit.

Table 26 - LR Fit Metrics

Region	LR, n=500, K=10				
	likelihood ratio	likelihood ratio p	likelihood ratio CoV	AIC	AIC CoV
RR1	22902	p < 0.001	0.43	33789	0.29
RR2	8069	p < 0.001	0.88	15481	0.46
RR3	6884	p < 0.001	1.27	23684	0.37
RR4	9090	p < 0.001	0.95	18296	0.47
RR5	7975	p < 0.001	0.08	84585	0.01
UR2	361	p < 0.001	6.19	2520	0.89
UR4	3431	p < 0.001	1.53	8549	0.62
UR5	13868	p < 0.001	0.53	25849	0.28

The interpretation gained from Table 26 is that while all of the models pass the likelihood ratio test, a few of them have higher variability in the likelihood ratio. The models for RR3, UR4, and especially UR2 all have higher CoV values indicating variability in the likelihood ratio. Additionally, the model for RR5 has a suspiciously low CoV value indicating that the likelihood ratio did not vary much at all between model runs. Based on these internal model metrics, it appears that the LR models are relatively stable for RR1, RR2, RR4, UR4, and UR5, but less so for UR2, UR4, and possibly RR5.

Adaptive Regression Splines. As discussed earlier in this report, adaptive regression splines are a special case of the GLM family of models that seek to approximate non-linear functions by using linear splines connected with hinge functions. This method has features not included in LR such as forward and backwards passes, variable selection, greater flexibility, and often a better trade-off between variance and goodness-of-fit (Freidman 1991). The forward pass of the model begins with just the intercept term, no predictors, and fits the model based on a reduced SSE. The forward pass then adds in the predictors and continues to fit until the SSE can be reduced no further. Known as a “greedy” algorithm, this forward pass often creates a very over-fit model—a model that represents the training data very well, but is not a good predictor. A backwards pass is then performed in which the forward pass model is recursively pruned to take away terms that add little to the overall model. This is termed “recursive” because unlike the forward pass, the backwards pass can see all of the prunes ahead of it and make decisions based on that. The pruned sub-models are then compared using a valued called the GCV to pick the best model; the lower the GCV the better the model. The methods of GCV and CV have some properties in common, but should not be confused as the same thing. GCV in the backwards pass of the adaptive regression splines is an index that approximates what a model’s error would be if regular CV was used (more specifically, leave-one-out validation). The GCV uses the Residual

Sum-of-Square (RSS) penalized by the number of model terms to find the best fit between goodness-of-fit and model complexity. The goal is to achieve the best fit without undue complexity.

The results of the adaptive regression spline produce a series of metrics that can be used to evaluate the model fit (RSS, R^2), stability (CoV), and estimated performance (GRSQ). Table 27 shows the internal metrics of the adaptive regression splines for all regions of the pilot model. The RSS is the total summed squared residuals from the linear fitted splines. The magnitude of this number will vary depending on the number of terms and data points, but the CoV is standardized. The R^2 is a measure of model fit ranging from 0 to 1, with 0 being a very poor fit and 1 a perfect fit. Finally, the GRSQ value is the estimate of the model's R^2 when predicting for independent data. The GRSQ will generally always be a bit less than the R^2 , but should not be significantly so if the model is a decent predictor. The CoV of the GRSQ and other metrics show the stability of the values across 500 repetitions of 10-fold CV.

From these results the models for RR1, RR2, RR4, UR4, and UR5 continue to look like relatively well-fit and stable models with a decent estimated prediction error. Model RR4 also appears to do well in the adaptive regression spline model. However, models UR2 and UR4 appear to be quite unstable, and RR5 is starting to suggest a relatively poor fit based on the R^2 and GRSQ values.

Table 27 - Adaptive Regression Splines Fit Metrics

Region	Adaptive Regression Splines, n=500, K=10					
	RSS	RSS CoV	R^2	R^2 CoV	GRSQ	GRSQ CoV
RR1	3188.221	0.727	0.523	0.664	0.522	0.667
RR2	1417.708	1.449	0.489	1.515	0.486	1.537
RR3	2204.795	0.922	0.389	1.451	0.387	1.444
RR4	1502.632	1.145	0.534	0.999	0.532	1.007
RR5	9152.745	0.329	0.161	1.717	0.160	1.703
UR2	167.395	3.606	0.509	3.484	0.489	3.746
UR4	771.234	1.695	0.457	2.015	0.452	2.053
UR5	2452.105	0.529	0.476	0.582	0.474	0.580

As part of the adaptive regression spline routine, a LR is performed. Table 28 reports the same model metrics as in Table 27, but from the GLM in the adaptive regression splines model. Comparing these two tables, it is clear that the likelihood ratio uniformly increased ($R^2 = 0.979$) and AIC uniformly decreased ($R^2 = 0.998$) across all models. This signifies better fit models with the adaptive regression splines. However, the variance of those measures increases across the board with the adaptive regression splines model: $R^2 = 0.934$ for the likelihood ratio CoV and

$R^2 = 0.782$ for the AIC CoV. Throughout the 5,000 runs of the adaptive regression splines model, it created generally better fit, but somewhat more variable models.

Table 28 - GLM Metrics Derived from Adaptive Regression Splines Models

Region	Adaptive Regression Splines, n=500, K=10				
	likelihood ratio	likelihood ratio p	likelihood ratio CoV	AIC	AIC CoV
RR1	25129	p < 0.001	0.58	31578	0.46
RR2	10967	p < 0.001	1.51	12602	1.32
RR3	9456	p < 0.001	0.95	21122	0.43
RR4	12948	p < 0.001	0.75	14457	0.67
RR5	11109	p < 0.001	0.08	81465	0.01
UR2	1317	p < 0.001	3.94	1580	3.24
UR4	4613	p < 0.001	1.53	7386	0.96
UR5	18201	p < 0.001	0.75	21535	0.63

Taken together, the results show model fits were better for the adaptive regression spline method, though somewhat more variable. In addition to the metrics that are shared between the two regression methods, the adaptive regression splines model reported additional metrics to help assess fit, stability, and prediction. The GRSQ value is the first look beyond model fit and into what level of prediction accuracy could be expected. While the GRSQ is only an estimate based on the GCV of the selected model versus the GCV of the null model, it does suggest that these models have a decent predictive utility (UR2 being a notable exception). The next chapter on model validation will get into more details on predictive utility.

Tree-Based Ensemble – RF. The final statistical function used in the pilot model to try and approximate Y is the tree-based RF method. The general concepts of RF were discussed earlier, but in essence the RF model builds numerous randomized classification trees to estimate the probability that a new observation belongs to a category, in this case site-presence or site-absence. The RF method has many benefits including parametric flexibility, bootstrapping, internal CV for unbiased performance estimates, scalability, and robust performance. Drawbacks to this model include relatively little ability to interpret predictor relationships, fewer metrics (possibly a pro), and the potential to “over fit” in some instances.

In a general sense, the process of the RF model begins by building a single decision tree with the key parameters of “mtry” (*em-try*), node size, and the number of trees (ntree). The tree begins by selecting a training set from the data provided; this typically equals about two-thirds of the data set. The remaining one-third is left aside—this is called OOB sample. The sampling of training and test samples is done randomly *with* replacement, so therefore is a bootstrapped sample. At

the first node, a subset of the predictor variables is chosen at random. By default, the number of randomly selected predictors, called *mtry*, is approximately one-third of the total number of predictors. Based on the randomly selected predictors, the node is split to best send each observation to its actual values (present or absent). This is repeated with a new set of *mtry* predictors randomly assigned at each node until the tree is fully grown and probabilities for the training data are computed (Figure 15). Following this, the OOB testing data are sent down the tree and through each node based on the split generated from the training data. Based on where the test data land, an error estimate is computed—this is called the OOB error. Additionally, if the test for variable importance is selected, an additional step is included that takes observations and passes them randomly through a node regardless of what the predictor suggests. If the error rate of the randomly split observation is similar to the non-randomized error rate, then the predictor at that node has little influence on the overall prediction. A metric of variable

Figure 15 - Schematic of basic decision tree.

importance is computed for each variable. After the tree is grown and tested, a second tree is grown in the same way but with a new bootstrapped random training and test sample and newly randomized predictors. This process is repeated for a larger number of trees (ntree); typically the resulting “forest” contains 500–1,000 trees. The prediction success, variable splits, and error rates are averaged across the entire forest and best node splits are selected.

The RF model was computed for each region of the pilot model study area that contained 10 or more sites. Each forest contained 500 trees and was repeated for each of 10-folds CV. This process was replicated five times with new random samples of 50,000 background data points. This totals 25,000 trees for each region. Like the previous statistical models, fit methods are computed, but unlike the previous models, the error estimates are performed on the independent OOB data, not estimated based on internal data. Table 29 lists the averaged metrics and CoV for all of the RF runs.

Table 29 - RF Internal Model Metrics

	RF, ntree=500, CV=10, n=5					
region	MSE	MSE CoV	RMSE	RMSE CoV	Pseudo-R ²	R ² CoV
RR1	0.054	1.359	0.233	0.680	0.783	0.376
RR2	0.036	3.338	0.190	1.666	0.855	0.565
RR3	0.107	0.612	0.326	0.305	0.574	0.455
RR4	0.039	2.403	0.199	1.211	0.842	0.451
RR5	0.113	0.462	0.336	0.230	0.548	0.382
UR2	0.015	7.889	0.123	3.949	0.939	0.512
UR4	0.016	2.401	0.125	1.203	0.937	0.162
UR5	0.021	1.673	0.144	0.822	0.916	0.153

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) and RMSE, the root of the MSE, are measures of how accurately the trees predict OOB observations. The MSE is the mean of squared residuals for each OOB observation for each tree. As the MSE approaches zero, the smaller the mean error between an observation and its predicted values becomes. The RMSE is a permutation of the MSE that is essentially the standard deviation of the prediction errors. Finally, the pseudo R-squared (pseudo R²) is a measure of the variation in Y that is represented by the model. The true R² measures the variance (subtly different from variation) in Y, but in general they are very comparable numbers. An R² or pseudo R² of one is a perfect prediction, whereas a value of zero or a negative number is a poor prediction.

The first impression of Table 29 is that for a number of regions, the pseudo R² shows a nearly perfect prediction. Further, the regions that were showing the best in previous models, such as RR1, appear to have lower pseudo R² values. Regions UR2 and UR4 seem to have very good

metrics in all categories at first blush, but the CoV shows that they are quite unstable. These seemingly counterintuitive measures are the result of the robust ability of the RF model to approximate probability and predict. The regions that fared poorly in the previous models had done so in part based on their small sample size. It was difficult for the previous models to find a solution for only a small number of site-present cells. The RF model, on the other hand, is better able to find the correct splits that lead to the proper classification of the small site samples and therefore have smaller prediction errors and higher pseudo R^2 . Though, as mentioned, the trade-off is a high CoV as the model's metrics vary based on the bootstrapped samples and randomized variables. From these results, it is pretty clear that the RF algorithm has little problem in correctly predicting site presence and absence based on the sample of known sites available. The question becomes, which datasets are these predictions useful for and how good of a prediction can we obtain and still feel comfortable that we are leaving room to find new sites that may not fall within the same pattern as exhibited by the known sites? The answer to the first question is that bigger datasets are better because the metrics for small datasets are overly optimistic and stability in the MSE appears to be a metric to follow. The validation procedures in the next section will shed more light on these results. The answer to the second question is ultimately subjective, but given the power of tools such as RF to very accurately define a pattern, it is likely that a dose of conservatism is needed to account for the bias we know exists within known site locations. Steps to address this issue will be presented later in this report.

As previously mentioned, Oehlert and Shea's (2007) assessment of the statistical underpinnings of the Mn Model evaluated a series of model types including perturbed tree-based methods. Their findings were that, "[o]verall, bagging, double bagging, and boosting had the best predictive ability" (Oehlert and Shea 2007:executive summary). The researchers found these tree-based methods to provide substantial improvements over the stepwise LR method used in the previous Mn Model. Within their tests, "double bagging" produced the best results, but they could not recommend it because of its difficulty to implement in GIS and the substantial computational cost of the algorithm when used with 11 trees ($n_{tree} = 11$). Fortunately, computer performance and algorithms have advanced since these findings and the barriers are lower. The RF method is a refinement of the bagging methods, which were created by the same researcher (Breiman 1996), and incorporate elements of boosting. Oehlert and Shea's findings are a strong testimonial for using tree-based models such as RF.

PILOT MODEL VALIDATION

The preceding section discussed the internal metrics of model fit and stability with the added metrics of GCV for the adaptive regression spline and OOB prediction errors for the RF model. Whereas in the previous section most of the comparisons were made between models within a region, in this section comparisons can be made between different models in different regions. This section reports on the validation of the models based on metrics derived from the OOS fold of the repeated K-folds CV. The values discussed in this section give a more realistic view of how well the models may predict in real world situations. Additionally, the metrics of this section will shed light on the variance and bias demonstrated by different models applied to the same datasets.

The judgmental and proportionally weighted models do not have a mechanism for practically deriving prediction errors based on the CV method. Models 1 and 2 require the creation of sensitivity raster GIS files and the extraction of those values at site locations in order to assess the fit. This process was only employed when data quality was very poor or it was clear that a model from the statistical class would not fit the data well. The results of those regions where Model Class 1 or 2 were selected will be presented in the model selection section. This section will present the results only for the eight regions where the statistical models were attempted.

The values tabulated in Table 30 represent the OOS prediction errors for each statistical model, for each modeled region. For LR and adaptive regression splines, these values are averaged over 10-folds CV repeated 500 times. For the RF model, the values are the means of 10 repetitions of 500 tree forests computed within 10-fold CV. For each model type, the values of AUC and RMSE are listed. The AUC is a single number used to represent the displacement of the ROC curve, which measures the balance between a model's sensitivity and specificity (Fawcett 2006). In the ROC curve, a null prediction is represented by a straight line from the origin (0,0) to the upper right corner. The better the model's ability to predict, the further toward the upper left corner of the graph (0,1) the ROC curve will be. The AUC value represents the area "under" the ROC curve and above the null prediction line. Therefore, an AUC of 0.5 is a null prediction and an AUC of 1 is a perfect prediction. Figure 16 is an example of an ROC curve with the null prediction line and values including the AUC and optimal cut-point (that is, the point on the curve closest to the 0,1 point). From a more technical point of view, the AUC value describes the model's ability to correctly classify random observations. According to Fawcett (2006:868), "[t]he AUC has an important statistical property: the AUC of a classifier is equivalent to the probability that the classifier will rank a randomly chosen positive instance higher than a randomly chosen negative instance."

Table 30 - Prediction Errors from Statistical Models

Region	LR, n=500, K=10		Adaptive Regression Splines, n=500, K=10		RF, trees=500, K=10	
	AUC	RMSE	AUC	RMSE	AUC	RMSE
RR1	0.897	0.351	0.914	0.333	0.973	0.274
RR2	0.871	0.385	0.910	0.345	0.989	0.271
RR3	0.814	0.417	0.851	0.386	0.922	0.352
RR4	0.876	0.370	0.918	0.329	0.987	0.264
RR5	0.708	0.469	0.733	0.456	0.924	0.442
UR2	0.736	0.455	0.913	0.327	0.999	0.099
UR4	0.849	0.401	0.896	0.360	0.999	0.152
UR5	0.863	0.388	0.898	0.358	0.999	0.186

Figure 16 - Example of ROC curve from the adaptive regression spline model from RR1.

In addition to the AUC, Table 30 compiles RMSE values for each model and region. Both of these measures are considered “loss functions” because they evaluate the difference between predicted values (\hat{y}) and the actual values (y) in the OOS test samples. The RMSE, as previously mentioned, is a standardized assessment of the average magnitude of differences between predicted and observed values. This measure is on the same scale as the response variable, so it ranges from zero to one, with a lower number signifying less error on average.

The values in Table 30 provide a valuable insight into the model’s ability to predict with independent (OOS) data. However, as with the previously discussed model internal metrics, care must be taken in interpreting these metrics because the structure of the data can have a great effect on the outcome. An immediate observation is that between each model type, from LR, to adaptive regression splines, to RF the error rates decrease and the AUC increases. Figure 17 charts the change in RMSE prediction error across each region for each model type. The charts are sorted by the values of the RF model. As with the model-internals metrics, it was apparent that the RF model would produce seemingly good results despite poor data quality. The figures in Table 30 and the charts confirm this for the OOS prediction errors. It would appear that the models for UR2 and UR4 are some of the best according to the AUC and RMSE of the RF model. However, we know that these data samples are biased by small size and are likely not representative of the total site population of those regions. Figure 17 demonstrates the variance between the error rates of the three different model types by the wide spread in the lines at the right hand side of the chart. While the RF appears to predict well, the lines for LR and adaptive regression splines document poor performance. As these models are less flexible than the RF, they do not over-fit the small samples. On the other hand, the higher RMSE for the RR5 corresponds to the lowest variance between the different model types. For RR5 the LR, adaptive regression splines, and RF models are all in close agreement to what the error rate should be. While the error rate is higher than some other regions, the models overall fit the structure of the data better. In the middle, the models for RR1, RR2, RR3, and RR4 appear to have moderate prediction errors and moderate variance between models.

Figure 17 – Averaged RMSE derived from 10-fold CV for each model and modeled region.

To aid in the understanding of these concepts, Figure 18 is an example of the predicted fit of an RF model for an OOS sample in Riverine Region 1. The y axis shows the predicted probability that a site-present cell (orange dots) or background cell (blue dots) is a site. (Note that the x-axis has no little meaning: the points are spread out according to their index number.) The black fit line is the approximated function (\hat{f}) and 95% confidence interval (gray shaded area). The RMSE is derived from the distance between each point (\hat{y}) and its true value (y); one for sites and zero for background. It is easy to see that a number of site-present cells are predicted to have relatively low probabilities, but most are close to a value of one. Conversely, the errors for the background are distributed randomly, but the mass of the data is predicted to be very close to zero. The prediction error of the background cells will be biased toward a higher value because many of those background cells (hopefully those higher on the graph) are truly site-present cells that have yet to be discovered. The red horizontal line in this figure is a decision boundary, which will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 18 – Example of RF model fit to OOS sample in RR1.

In total, these results show that the prediction errors and AUC range from region to region and model to model. The values for both LR and adaptive regression splines models are within expectations given the model-internal metric and understanding of the data structure (e.g., number of sites, distributions, site size, clustering). The values for the RF model add a new element because the model flexibility allows it to fit and predict when the data structure inhibited the previous model types. The very high AUC and low RMSE of the RF models for some regions are a strong signal that these models are likely over-fit and may not be appropriate for the underlying data. The final step of evaluation applies the models to each study area and assesses the on-the-ground fit of the entire site sample and the total background.

PILOT MODEL - MODEL SELECTION AND FINALIZATION

Based on the previous discussion, it is clear that different measures of a model are capable of giving contradictory or unclear results. This has as much to do with the differences between statistical methods and the various sources of error within and between models as it does with the bias of the underlying dataset. Choosing the “best” model to represent a region is, unfortunately, not as simple as choosing the model with the best numbers. As we have seen, the RF models are extremely capable of accurately predicting the location of the known site-present cells even when other models had trouble doing so. We have also seen that the less flexible LR and adaptive regression spline models are capable of achieving fits and error rates that are comparable with other published APMs, but they do so with more generality. The take-away from the previous discussion is that we have flagged a few region and model combinations that appear to have higher variance, bias, and may have underlying data structures with a high degree of noise; UR2 is at the top of that list. However, in general, the models for most regions are behaving as expected with reasonable error rates, relatively good stability, and fits that are commensurate with each method’s flexibility and limitations.

KVAMME GAIN CURVES

The final model selection is done by comparing the internal metrics, prediction errors, and sensitivity/specificity curves, visualizing the prediction relative to the site sample (e.g., data structure), and then viewing the Kg relative to the range of cut-points to segment site-likely (high and moderate sensitivity), from site-unlikely (low sensitivity). Figure 19 shows the Kg curves for each model type and each region. In these graphs, the x-axis is the percent site-present cells and the y-axis is the percent background cells. As a reminder, the Kg is the ratio between how many site-present locations are predicted for within how much of the study area. It is calculated as:

$$Kg = 1 - \frac{\% \text{ background cells in site - likely area}}{\% \text{ site - present cells in site - likely area}}$$

In Figure 19, the “ideal” curve will be very close to the lower right-hand corner. A curve that follows along the bottom and then shoots up at the end demonstrates a model that contains a large portion of the known sites within a small portion of the study area. In theory, this is a good prediction for archaeology because it pinpoints those locations that we believe are sensitive for sites, based on known sites, and excludes large areas that do not fit the pattern, thereby saving time and effort in site survey. However, if we simply maximize the model for Kg, we are likely to produce a model that excludes areas that may be only somewhat similar to those containing

sites or locations that contain sites that are not represented in our known sample. In this case, we are likely to encounter sites in areas we do not expect them—a costly error.

The curves depicted in Figure 19 are a sort of visual synthesis of the previous findings and give a sense of the real-world application and behavior of each model. For example, the curves for RR1 indicate what is most likely the best set of models in the pilot study. The uniform pitch across the entire model, closeness of the three lines, and position near, but not deep within, the lower right-hand corner signify model agreement and good prediction. Conversely, the curves for UR2 show very erratic models that are in no agreement. For UR2, the LR model (orange solid line) is almost a null prediction. The RMSE of 0.455 and AUC of 0.736 indicate that this model was performing rather poorly. For the same region, the adaptive regression splines (Earth) model achieves some utility, but is not a smooth curve. Additional erratic model behavior can be seen in the curves for RR2 and in the adaptive regression splines model of UR4.

Another observation of Figure 19 is that the curves for the RF model are consistently deep into the lower right-hand corner while the LR and adaptive regression spline model curves are often closer together. This trend was seen in the previous results where the regression methods produced similar results, with a slight edge going to the adaptive regression splines model. We also saw that the RF model would correctly assign probabilities, especially with limited datasets. This result is concurrent with the expectations of the method. However, since our objective is to have a model that is more liberal than the RF results, but perhaps more conservative than the LR or adaptive regression splines, we can combine the two model results into a hybrid model that exhibits the characteristics of each.

An unfortunate consequence of achieving better predictions through combining models is that it adds another layer between the prediction and our ability to identify potential explanatory connections within the models. This is true for any form of empirical modeling: the more flexible the model is in drawing predictions from noisy data, the less explanatory the results. Since the goal of this project is to develop accurate representations of site location sensitivity primarily for planning purposes, however, the goal of explanation is secondary. There are other statistical methods that are more appropriate for seeking causal relationships than those used for prediction. Nonetheless, some of the results produced from this study, such as the coefficient estimates from the LR and the variable importance derived from the RF models, can form the basis of explanatory research.

Figure 19 - Distribution of Kg statistics for each model in all of the modeled regions.

MODEL COMBINATION

Combining model results is a relatively simple task of combining the predicted probabilities for a single region from two or more models. These probabilities can be combined by taking the averaged, minimum, maximum, or other permutation of probability for each overlapping cell. Each method of combining draws certain characteristics from each model. For example, the averaging of two different models will bias the results to the model with the greater number of extreme values. In this case that is the RF model. On the other hand, taking the maximum of each model will essentially take the “best guess” and produce a more even spread of probability values. Alternatively, taking the maximum probability for each cell between two models will “take the best of both worlds” by expanding the highly specific RF model to include areas that the more general model felt was sensitive. This method raises the overall probability distribution of the model, which is a good thing when it is being raised from the very threshold-dependent RF model. Figure 20 is a comparison of the change in Kg across the predicted probabilities for the basic statistical models, LR and RF, as well as the two hybrid models of LR/RF average (red line) and LR/RF maximum (blue line). The averaged model hybrid tends to bias toward the RF and the maximum model hybrid more evenly divides the gain.

Figure 20 - UR4: Comparison of Kg across the modeled probabilities for statistical models and hybrid models.

MODEL SELECTION

Model selection proceeded by using the above validation and testing results in conjunction with the Kg distribution calculated for each model to establish the cut-point between site-likely (high and moderate sensitivity) and site-unlikely (low sensitivity) areas. At the beginning of the study, there were no established parameters for how to divide these classes, only the findings of previous studies reviewed in Task 1 and the idea that “more sites in less space is good.” During the model building process it became apparent that the inclusion of newer models such as adaptive regression splines and RF gave us a set of tools that changed the perspective to “how much background area do we include to limit false-negatives?” Previously APM was often a search to make generalized predictions more specific, but when the data quality allows for the use of better models, we seek to make specific predictions more general. The amount of generality is based in part on the prediction error metrics and model stability, but also the intuition gained from understanding the site patterns and bias on each region. However, intuition is not much of a guideline, so more appropriate measures are required.

Oehlert and Shea (2007) recommend that model selection should be based on achieving the highest true-positive rate (TPR), termed “Sensitivity,” and true negative rate (TNR), termed “Specificity.” Model sensitivity (described as “completeness” in the Task 1 report) is the total fraction of sites that are classified by the model to be in the site-likely area. Specificity (described as “efficiency” in the Task 1 report) is the fraction of background that is classified as site-unlikely by the model. As described throughout the reports in this project, the goal of an APM is not necessarily to maximize these two fractions, but to find a balance between them that makes sense given the application and site data structure.

A model that predicts the entire study area as site-likely will have a sensitivity of one because it correctly classifies all sites, but it will have a specificity of zero because it incorrectly classifies every background or non-site point. Conversely, an entirely specific model will have a sensitivity of zero because it classifies the entire study area as site-unlikely. However, these numbers are not inversely proportional, so a model can be both specific and sensitive. A model that is highly specific and highly sensitive will correctly classify most of the sites as sites and most of the background as site-unlikely. As summarized by Oehlert and Shea:

Ideally, both the sensitivity and the specificity of a method are high. If Rule 1 were both more sensitive and more specific than Rule 2, we would clearly prefer Rule 1. However, when one of the predictors is more sensitive and the other is more specific, we have to decide which errors are more costly before we can choose between the rules. For example, if the costs associated with happening upon an archaeological site at a location that was predicted as a non-site are much greater than the costs of unnecessarily surveying a location or unnecessarily avoiding portions of the landscape (avoiding

predicted sites that were actually non-sites), then we will prefer the more sensitive method. (Oehlert and Shea 2007:4)

This relationship can be visualized by the ROC curves; an example is given for the adaptive regression spline model of RR1 in Figure 16. A ROC curve is the intersection of sensitivity and 1-specificity across the entire range of cut-points for a given model. As labeled on the graphic, the sensitivity is 88.4% and the specificity is 77.4%. The AUC figures detailed in the validation section are a single number summation that is related to the ratio of sensitivity to specificity. In general, the higher the sensitivity and specificity the higher the ROC curve and the higher the AUC. Oehlert and Shea (2007:13–14) recommend that the selected models should seek to achieve a sensitivity of 85% (85% of the sites correctly classified) and then maximize for specificity. If multiple candidate models achieve a specificity of 85%, then the model that minimizes the false-positives (1-specificity) should be selected. This would achieve the goal of correctly classifying a large percent of the known sites into as small of a site-likely area as the model will allow. The pilot model followed this recommendation for the more restrictive LR and adaptive regression splines models. The model-flexible RF model results do not adhere to this rule because along with very high sensitivity they often achieve a specificity that is too high given the errors inherent in archaeological data and the goal of the models. For these situations, the hybrid models were created to retain the model’s high sensitivity, but decrease the specificity (increase the area of false-positives) to a more acceptable level. As recommended by Oehlert and Shea, these decisions were made on the ROC curves and accompanying metrics derived from OOS predictions.

SELECTED MODELS

Table 31 lists the K_g value for the cut-off between high and moderate sensitivity (site-likely) and low sensitivity (site-unlikely) for each final model selected for each region. Also, this table lists the final model that was selected to represent each region. Appendix C is a list of tables for each of the eight regions where statistical models were attempted. These tables include the percent sites, percent background area, K_g , and high and moderate cut points for the probability distribution of each model.

Table 31 - Final Model Kg and Model Selection for All Regions of the Pilot Model

Region	Count of PASS sites	Kg at selected site-likely cut-point						Selected Model
		Model Class 1	Model Class 2	LR	Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)	Hybrid Model	RF	
Region 1	52							
Upland	2	0.389	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	Model Class 1
Riverine	50		0.588	0.679	0.686	0.685	0.816	Earth/RF max
Region 2	79							
Upland	19		0.692	0.488	0.930	n/a	1.000	Model Class 2
Riverine	60		0.511	0.487	0.702	n/a	0.886	Model Class 2
Region 3	53							
Upland	1	0.389	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	Model Class 1
Riverine	52		0.615	0.519	0.651	n/a	0.811	Model Class 2
Region 4	96							
Upland	40		0.543	0.636	0.828	0.833	0.953	LR/RF max
Riverine	56		0.523	0.664	0.671	0.804	0.803	Earth/RF avg
Region 5	612							
Upland	166		0.533	0.549	0.638	0.614	0.860	Earth/RF avg
Riverine	446		0.316	0.388	0.456	0.754	0.731	Earth/RF avg

SELECTED MODEL PERFORMANCE

The final evaluation of each applied model is through the use of the classification table referred to as a confusion matrix (Fawcett 2006). While understanding the implications of these 2×2 contingency tables may be a bit “confusing” at first, the name is actually derived from understanding how “confused” the model was in its classification. Similar contingency tables were used in the evaluation of APM in the Task 1 report. The appendix of that report goes into more discussion of how the tables are created and used. However, a quick recap is provided here (Table 32).

Table 32 - Schematic of Confusion Matrix and Related Assessment Measures

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	True Positive (A)	False Positive (B)	Total Predicted Sites (A+B)
	Absent	False Negative (C)	True Negative (D)	Total Predicted Non-sites (C+D)
		Total Sites (A+C)	Total Background (B+D)	

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Sensitivity / TPR} &= A/(A+C) \\
 \text{Specificity / TNR} &= D/(B+D) \\
 \text{Prevalence} &= (A+C)/(A+B+C+D) \\
 \text{Kvamme Gain (Kg)} &= 1-(B/(B+D))/(A/(A+C)) \\
 \text{Accuracy} &= (A+D)/(A+B+C+D) \\
 \text{Positive Prediction Value (PPV)} &= A/(A+B) \\
 \text{Negative Prediction Value (NPV)} &= D/(D+C) \\
 \text{Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR)} &= 1 - \text{NPV} \\
 \text{Positive Prediction Gain (PPG)} &= \text{PPV}/\text{Prevalence} \\
 \text{Negative Prediction Gain (NPG)} &= \text{UDR}/\text{Prevalence} \\
 \text{False Negative Rate (FNR)} &= C/(A+C)
 \end{aligned}$$

Simply, the confusion matrix is a 2×2 table that shows how many sites were correctly predicted as sites and how much of the non-site area was correctly predicted as such. Associated with the confusion matrix are a series of measurements derived from different combinations of the cells. Listed in Table 32 are some of the measurements relevant to assessing these APMs. Sensitivity and specificity were previously defined as the true-positive and true-negative rates, respectively. Prevalence is the real-world probability that any given point is a site; this is based on how many known sites are in a region. The Kg has been previously discussed. Accuracy is the percent of correct site and background predictions. The next two measurements, the Positive Prediction Value (PPV) and Negative Prediction Value (NPV) are the probability that a site is correctly labeled as a site or a background cell is correctly labeled as such. Similarly, the Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) is $1 - \text{NPV}$: the fraction of sites in the site-unlikely area. The three values (PPV, NPV, and UDR) are included here, but when the confusion matrix is built to consider the

performance of the full model, they have little relevance in their raw form. These measures use the false-positive and true-negative rates in their calculations and since we are looking at the full area model there are vastly more truly site-absent cells than site-present. This imbalance is reflected in the very low prevalence values for each of these models. On average, the modeled regions of the pilot model study had a prevalence of 0.009 (0.9 % of the area), ranging from a prevalence of 0.03 to 0.0005. In order to assess performance in light of the very low prevalence of archaeological sites in the modeled regions, the next two measures on that list consider this imbalance. The PPG and Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) are ratios of the PPV and UDR to the prevalence of known sites. The PPG measures how much more likely we are to find a site in the site-likely prediction area than survey at random. Similarly, the NPG measures the odds of finding an archaeological site in the site-unlikely area compared to survey at random. A good prediction will have a high PPG and a low NPG. The final measure listed in Table 32 is the false-negative rate (FNR). This is an important number that gives the fraction of the known site cells that are not included within the site-likely area. This number is not influenced by the imbalance of the background cells and should be minimized. Following the recommendations of Oehlert and Shea (2007), the goal is to keep this number below 0.15, or 15% of the site-present cells misclassified. Tables 33–40 are the results, in confusion matrix form, for the final models applied to each of the eight regions where a statistical model was applied.

Table 33 - Results for Riverine Region 1 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	13711	199868	213579
	Absent	0	435278	435278
		13711	635146	

- Sensitivity / TPR = 1.000
- Specificity / TNR = 0.685
- Prevalence = 0.021
- Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.685
- Accuracy = 0.692
- Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.064
- Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
- Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
- Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 3.038
- Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.000
- False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.000

Table 34 - Results for Riverine Region 2 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	5092	362665	367757
	Absent	691	478979	479670
		5783	841644	

Sensitivity / TPR = 0.881
 Specificity / TNR = 0.569
 Prevalence = 0.007
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.511
 Accuracy = 0.571
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.014
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 0.999
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.001
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 2.029
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.211
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.119

Table 35 - Results for Riverine Region 3 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	7397	100081	107478
	Absent	608	137826	138434
		8005	237907	

Sensitivity / TPR = 0.924
 Specificity / TNR = 0.579
 Prevalence = 0.033
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.545
 Accuracy = 0.591
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.069
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 0.996
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.004
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 2.114
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.135
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.076

Table 36 - Results for Riverine Region 4 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	6473	467393	473866
	Absent	0	1912009	1912009
		6473	2379402	

Sensitivity / TPR = 1.000
 Specificity / TNR = 0.804
 Prevalence = 0.003
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.804
 Accuracy = 0.804
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.014
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 5.035
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.000
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.000

Table 37 - Results for Riverine Region 5 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	21982	789168	811150
	Absent	67	2427754	2427821
		22049	3216922	

Sensitivity / TPR = 0.997
 Specificity / TNR = 0.755
 Prevalence = 0.007
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.754
 Accuracy = 0.756
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.027
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 3.981
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.004
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.003

Table 38 - Results for Upland Region 2 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	742	4173823	4174565
	Absent	15	9670128	9670143
		757	13843951	

Sensitivity / TPR = 0.980
 Specificity / TNR = 0.699
 Prevalence = 0.000
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.692
 Accuracy = 0.699
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.000
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 3.251
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.028
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.020

Table 39 - Results for Upland Region 4 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	3156	4464563	4467719
	Absent	0	22213761	22213761
		3156	26678324	

Sensitivity / TPR = 1.000
 Specificity / TNR = 0.833
 Prevalence = 0.000
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.833
 Accuracy = 0.833
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.001
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 5.972
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.000
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.000

Table 40 - Results for Upland Region 5 Model

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	10370	8434422	8444792
	Absent	0	13393206	13393206
		10370	21827628	

Sensitivity / TPR = 1.000
 Specificity / TNR = 0.614
 Prevalence = 0.000
 Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.614
 Accuracy = 0.614
 Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.001
 Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
 Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
 Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 2.586
 Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.000
 False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.000

Returning to Figure 18, the relationship between false and true positive and negatives can be visualized. The horizontal red line in this plot presents a decision boundary between site-likely (high and moderate sensitivity) and site-unlikely (low sensitivity). Every orange site-present dot above that decision boundary is a true-positive; those below the boundary are false-negatives. For the blue background dots, those above the boundary are false-positives and below the boundary are true-negatives. Ideally, we want to minimize the false-negatives (increase sensitivity) and reduced the false-positives (increase specificity), but in reality false-negatives are a more costly error. We need a healthy portion of false-positives because this is the region that contains our sensitive landforms and undiscovered sites. If the fraction of false-positives is too high, however, then our model is diluted because it predicts unnecessarily large areas as sensitive (low specificity). The values listed for each confusion matrix help us understand this balance.

The results in the above matrices show the ability of each region’s model to correctly and incorrectly classify site-present cells into site-present (high and moderate sensitivity) and site-absent (low sensitivity) classes. The metrics that accompany each matrix reveal the model’s classification ability from a number of perspectives. While, unfortunately, there is no single number that sums up all dimensions of model performance, the metrics listed are the most telling

and appropriate for our goals. The metrics that help give the best “at-a-glance” performance measure are the Kg, PPG, NPG, and FNR.

Simply, the Kg tells us how the model is balanced between correctly classifying a large percent of the sites while reducing the area in which they are predicted. Very generally, a model that is balanced to minimize false-negatives at the expense of false-positives will have a Kg in the neighborhood of 0.55 to 0.85. Performance at the expense of a high false-positive rate is a key feature for APM. This is due to the somewhat unique feature associated with archaeological site data: because we use the full environmental background as our site-absent sample, the models consider many locations that have undiscovered sites as site-absent. Therefore, we must set the cut-point rather low to capture the background cells with the higher predicted probabilities. This constitutes the areas where we are “predicting” sites may be. If a study area has a large portion of attractive landscapes that have no recorded sites due to lack of survey, then we want them to be labeled as site-likely, thereby making them a false-positive. In other predictive studies, this situation is not as common. Generally, positive and negative observations are rather clear cut, but in archaeology we know there are many sites out there that have yet to be discovered. The alternative—that is, using only areas cleared for the presence of archaeology sites as site-absent—has its own host of issues that unfortunately outweigh optimization at the expense of a higher false-positive rate.

The PPG and NPG, as discussed earlier, are the odds of finding a site where the model suggests there may be one as opposed to at random (PPG) and the odds of finding a site were we say there should *not* be one as opposed to surveying at random (NPG). For example, in Table 33, the PPG value shows that you are three times more likely to find a site in high or moderate probability areas than by surveying at random. The NPG shows a negligible chance, based on this model, of finding a site in a low probability area. These numbers depend, of course, on the bias inherent in the site types and locations of the known sample, but in general the higher the PPG and lower the NPG, the greater the utility of the model. Finally, the FNR is the measure of the fraction of cells that are recorded to contain sites that are classified as low probability. The trick of these models is to minimize this number as a trade-off to increasing the false-positive rate. As expressed above, a lower FNR is much more desirable than a lower false-positive rate. The cells included within the FNR may be located on the periphery of known sites, or they may be of a different site type, focused on different environments, or just outliers for one reason or another. There will almost always be a FNR of some magnitude, but keeping it under 0.15 is a reasonable goal.

FINAL MODEL PERFORMANCE

The final model that represents the predicted sensitivity of the entire pilot model study area is created by mosaicking the 10 regional models into a single raster (Figure 21). Table 41 is the

confusion matrix for the full ensemble model that covers the entire pilot model study area. As shown in the metrics, this model hits our goal of correctly classifying 85% of the site-present cells at the expense of a 0.149 FNR. This model correctly classifies 85% of the site-present cells within a site-likely area of 15.2% of the total pilot model study area. This equates to a Kg of 0.821—a successful effort. Finally, the odds of finding a site in high or moderate sensitivity areas (PPG) are 5.56 times that of surveying at random, while the odds of accidentally finding sites in the low sensitivity area (NPG) is 0.175. These results, combined with the understanding of prediction error from the CV procedures, describe a model that is successful at assessing the sensitivity of archaeological site locations and is balanced to compensate for the biases of archaeological data. Appendix D contains a 1:105,000-scale atlas of the pilot model study area overlain with the final sensitivity assessment; the raster data set is also supplied in order to facilitate scale manipulation.

Table 41 - Results for Combined Pilot Model Predictive Models

		Known Sites		
		Present	Absent	
Model Prediction	Present	63337	12980007	13043344
	Absent	11050	72155399	72166449
		74387	85135406	

- Sensitivity / TPR = 0.851
- Specificity / TNR = 0.848
- Prevalence = 0.001
- Kvamme Gain (Kg) = 0.821
- Accuracy = 0.848
- Positive Prediction Value (PPV) = 0.005
- Negative Prediction Value (NPV) = 1.000
- Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR) = 0.000
- Positive Prediction Gain (PPG) = 5.562
- Negative Prediction Gain (NPG) = 0.175
- False Negative Rate (FNR) = 0.149

Figure 21 - Overview of prehistoric sensitivity model for the pilot study area; scale 1:1,000,000.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The previous sections describe a system for creating sensitivity models that includes data preparation and evaluation, the construction of three different model types, the evaluation of models through internal fit metrics and prediction errors derived from K-folds CV, model selection, and finally the compilation of models into an ensemble. The final model for the pilot area was able to correctly classify 85% of the site-present cells into approximately 15% of the study area: a K_g of 0.821. Compared to random survey, the chances of finding a site in high or moderate sensitivity areas are 5.56 times greater. Similarly, the odds of finding sites in low probability areas are 0.175 times that of random survey. From the model validation steps, it was shown that a number of the statistical models have moderate to good performance when tested against the OOS datasets in the CV procedure. These numbers describe a model that is successful at assessing the sensitivity of archaeological site locations and has prediction errors that are commensurate with data quality. Where the validation and model fit are unstable, the statistical models were replaced with more conservative proportionally weighted models that make fewer assumptions.

In all, the procedures developed through the pilot model process are able to evaluate large amounts of data and create successful models in a consistent and replicable manner. Most of the steps of this process are partially automated through the use of scripts and functions. This process generates reliable and useful metrics that can be evaluated objectively. This “human touch” is a key feature of model building for any discipline, and perhaps more so for archaeology because of the very complex unmodeled human component that led directly to the creation of the settlement patterns that we study. This is compounded by the complex human behavior that leads to the discovery of the prehistoric settlement pattern in our modern times. These and a host of additional complications make the modeling of archaeological sensitivity a non-trivial task that requires numerous assumptions and considerations in order to be successful.

While the pilot model process was successful, it also exposed a number of issues and inefficiencies that could be addressed in upcoming state-wide implementation. Listed below are a series of recommendations that include methodological and statistical issues that we feel may improve the results of the future models and give a better sense of prediction errors.

PROCEDURAL RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Consider replacing the judgmentally weighted model with statistical models.
 - The application of Model Class 1, and to a lesser degree Model Class 2, is intended to derive an assessment of sensitivity in areas with low data quality that cannot support the assumptions of the statistical models. An alternative approach would be to shift these assumptions to another region with better data quality if the similarity of their background environments can be statistically verified. The benefit would be a more unified approach with potentially better-fitting models to poor data areas. The drawback is in applying models with greater assumptions to areas that may or may not support those assumptions.
2. Experiment with a variation of the proportionally weighted Model Class 2.
 - Currently, Model Class 2 assigns weights based on the proportion of known site-cells that fall within each class of a predictor variable. In the Task 1 report (Harris 2013a), a variation of this developed by Whitley and Bastianini (1992) was discussed. Their method does a similar proportional weighting, but takes an extra step to add negative weights based on the proportion of background cells. This method may be better able to distinguish site-likely locations, but would need to be tested against the current method.
3. Standardize and add new possible predictor variables.
 - With many of the predictors in the pilot model study, a neighborhood of cells was required to compute the statistic. In the future studies, the range of neighborhoods will be standardized across these variables. In addition, a few new variables will be added including Euclidian and cost-distance to Wallace’s (1965) “Indian Paths” and possibly soils data.

MODELING/STATISTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Revise CV methods to be spatially segregated.
 - Currently, the CV methods employed in this model iterate over site-present cells randomly selected from all of the site-present cells regardless of their location. Oehlert and Shea (2007) recommend a spatially segregated CV procedure that chooses the CV samples based on site clustering—a spatially stratified random sample as opposed to a purely random sample. Implementation would require the clustering of sites, likely using the nearest neighbor algorithm, and the selection of OOS tests to be from clusters that were not utilized in the model creation. This will most likely give a more realistic assessment of model performance on new and independent data.

2. Experiment with rare-event modeling methods to find the optimal balance between site-present and background cells.
 - As stated in the report, there are two broad methods for handling rare events, through model weighting or sampling. The pilot model utilizes balanced sampling bootstrapped over hundreds of replications to simulate a diverse background population. In the future models more thought should be given to incorporating model weighting to help offset the bias against rare events.
3. Incorporate additional variables and variable interaction into the statistical models.
 - In the pilot model study, the statistical models use only the few predictor variables that were found to discriminate site locations well and did not introduce added spatial autocorrelation. This method is sound and computationally efficient, but the models may be missing important predictors or the interaction between predictors that were dropped in the predictor screening. The downside of adding more variables is an increase in computation time, decrease in model parsimony, and possible issues with over-fitting, although adaptive regression splines and RF can account for this. In future models, we will use stepwise procedures to evaluate models over a series of variable selections.
4. Incorporate soils data into the modeling process.
 - The predictor variables used in the pilot model study were, for the most part, related to derivations of elevation, slope, and hydrology.. While these worked well in the pilot model region, which was a ridge and valley setting, they may have less discriminatory power in areas with little topographic relief and more widespread water sources, such as the near-coast settings in the southeastern part of the state or near Lake Erie in the northwestern corner of the state. Soils data present issues that would need to be surmounted, but they should be explored as an additional source of discriminant variables. In order to make them useful, soils data will need to be aggregated for each spatial soil map unit. Attributes that may be useful include flood frequency, ponding frequency, water storage capacity, drainage class, capability classification, bedrock depth, and hydric condition. Once aggregated, each of these attributes should be tested to determine if they have the potential to help distinguish archaeological site locations in different physiographic settings. Variables found to help distinguish archaeological sites should be incorporated into future models.
5. Include rock shelters and quarry sites in the predictive models.
 - Steep slopes (equal to or greater than 15%) were excluded from the pilot model for two main reasons: first, because including steep slopes would dilute the model and result in large areas of false positives and second, because the Pennsylvania guidelines for archaeological survey requires that all steeply sloped areas be pedestrian surveyed to identify possible rock shelters and micro-topographical

features. Excluding these areas from the model does not suggest they have no archaeological potential, but acknowledges that they are best handled in the manner outlined in the guidelines. Some regions, however, have large numbers of rock shelters and/or quarry sites, both of which often occur on steep slopes. Two approaches are recommended to address the issue of rock shelters and quarries: 1) experiment with producing models that do not exclude 15% and greater slopes to determine how much this affects the success of predicting for open-air sites; and 2) attempt to make separate rock shelter and open-air site models in subareas that have a high percent of recorded rock shelters within them. It is not recommended that geologic formations be used as an additional discriminant variable. The reason for this is that, although rock shelters and quarries are often found in areas of similar bedrock geology, they make up only a very small fraction of those areas and are formed by very localized effects such as steepness, intra-bedrock members, bedrock inclusions, fractures/faults, and erosion. These localized effects are incongruous with the scale at which bedrock is mapped (see Pennsylvania Bureau of Topographic and Geologic Survey [2001] for usage constraints and Openshaw [1983] for a discussion of the modifiable areal unit problem), and it is very unlikely that the statistical models will be able to identify the localized effects that lead to rock shelters and quarries.

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APPENDIX A
ACRONYMS AND GLOSSARY OF TERMS

ACRONYMS

AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
APM	Archaeological Predictive Modeling
AUC	Area Under Curve
AUROC	Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristics Curve
CART	Classification and Regression Trees
CoV	Coefficient of Variation
CRGIS	Cultural Resources Geographic Information System
CV	Cross-Validation
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
FNR	False Negative Rate
FPR	False Positive Rate
GCV	Generalized Cross-Validation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GLM	Generalized Linear Models
GRSQ	Generalized R-Square
Kg	Kvamme Gain
K-S	Kolmogorov–Smirnov
LR	Logistic Regression
MARS	Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimate
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MW	Mann-Whitney
NPG	Negative Prediction Gain
NPV	Negative Prediction Value
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
OOB	Out-of-bag Sample
OOS	Out-of-Sample

PASS	Pennsylvania Archaeological Site Survey
PPG	Positive Predictive Gain
PPV	Positive Prediction Value
R ²	R-Squared
RF	Random Forests/randomForest
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristics
RSS	Residual Sum-of-Squares
SD	Standard Deviation
SSE	Sum of Squares Error
TNR	True-Negative Rate
TPR	True-Positive Rate
UDR	Unexpected Discovery Rate

TERMS

	page in report text (first used)
Adaptive Regression Splines (see Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines [†])	16
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).....	51
A measure of relative model quality that balances goodness of fit and model complexity. This measure is used in model selection to choose the model that has the best fit relative to complexity for a given data set. Within a series of nested candidate models, the one with the lowest AIC will likely represent the model with the best goodness of fit without being over-fit or over-parameterized (see Akaike 1974).	
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).....	47
ANOVA is a suite of statistical models used to test the difference in variation between groups. In linear model creation, ANOVA can be used to estimate the variance explained by each variable or whether there is a significant difference in variance explained by each model (see Freedman 2005).	
Archaeological Predictive Modeling (APM)	2
The field of study concerning the use of existing archaeological data or theory to predict the sensitivity of locations for the presence of archaeological material.	
Area Under Curve (AUC) (see also Receiver Operating Characteristics)	21
Also referred to as Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristics Curve (AUROC), AUC is a measure of the balance between a model's Sensitivity and Specificity across the full range of cut-off points. The AUC is a single measure that captures a model's ability to balance True Positive Rate and False Positive Rate across the full range of the model's output. The higher the AUC, the higher the Sensitivity and Specificity across the full range of the model, and the more likely the model is to correctly classify a randomly chosen positive instance. AUC is used in model selection to assess a model's ability to correctly classify observations (see Fawcett 2006).	
Bagging (see Bootstrap Aggregating)	18

[†] Bolded text indicates a term that is defined elsewhere in the glossary.

Boosting.....	20
<p>Boosting is a term that defines a family of statistical regression and classification methods that use random subset selection and weighting to minimize variance and lessen the potential for over-fitting. The concept of boosting is used in a number of regression and classification models with the general commonality of providing a means to achieve an ensemble of models. The final model is often selected through the weighted average of sub-models (see Freund and Schapire 1997).</p>	
Bootstrap Aggregating.....	18
<p>Bootstrap Aggregating (or Bagging) is a term that defines a method of statistical regression and classification often applied to tree-based machine learning algorithms. Simply, bagging uses the regression or classification of numerous bootstrapped samples to create an ensemble. Taking the average output of this ensemble generally reduces model variance and lessens the potential for over-fitting (Breiman 1996a).</p>	
Bootstrapping.....	14
<p>Bootstrapping is a statistical method of resampling that draws numerous samples from a sample or population with replacement. This means that each time a sample is chosen, its value is returned to the sampling population so that it may be drawn again. Bootstrapping offers a method of estimating population parameters from small samples or complicated distributions (see Efron and Tibshirani 1993).</p>	
Classification and Regression Trees (CART).....	18
<p>CART is a statistical learning algorithm. In a simple form, the CART is used to classify training observations based on the nested splitting of input variables. Called nodes, the split point of each variable creates a branch-like structure that begins with all of the training observations at the base of the tree and ends with the classification of each training observation at the tips of each branch. A predictive model can be drawn from the ability of the tree to correctly classify training and test observations based on the splits in each variable. The general structure of the CART is used as the basis for a number of algorithms such as Bagging, Boosting, and Random Forest (see Breiman et al. (1984).</p>	
Confusion Matrix.....	35
<p>A classification table in the form of a 2-cell × 2-cell contingency table that shows how many sites were correctly predicted as sites and how much of the non-site area was correctly predicted as such. This method is frequently used as a means to assess the ability of a model to classify observations (see Fawcett 2006).</p>	

Cost Variable7
A Cost Variable is a predictive variable derived through a cost analysis. The cost associated with a cost variable may be anything that is thought to introduce a difficulty or impediment to movement. For example, the linear distance for any point to the nearest stream only considers the straight line distance between those two points. A cost distance to the nearest stream will consider an impediment or set of impediments between any given point and the nearest stream. If crossing a wetland is considered costly, the least cost path from a given point may not be the shortest linear path, but may be a non-linear path that avoids traveling over wetlands.

Coefficient of Variation (CoV).....21
The CoV is a statistic that measures the normalized dispersion within a frequency distribution. The acronym CoV is used in this study to avoid confusion with the acronym used for **Cross-Validation** (CV). The CoV is calculated as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean and is also referred to as Relative Standard Deviation (RSD). The CoV represents the percentage of standard deviation from the sample mean (see Lehmann 1986).

Cross-Validation (CV) (see **Generalized Cross Validation** and **K-folds Cross-Validation**)14

Cultural Resources Geographic Information System (CRGIS)5
Computerized database and mapping tool for the visualization and analysis of cultural resources data within the Commonwealth of Pennsylvania. This tool is developed and administered through a joint agreement between the Pennsylvania Historical and Museum Commission and the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. (This tool is available at: www.portal.state.pa.us/portal/server.pt/community/crgis/3802.)

Digital Elevation Model (DEM)7
A digital elevation model is a computer based representation of the topography at earth’s surface. DEMs are stored as a raster format composed of square cells representing a single elevation measure for a given resolution. DEMs are available in a range of resolutions and are created and curated by the United States Geologic Survey. (Information and data sets are available at: <http://ned.usgs.gov>.)

Earth (see also **Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines**)16
Earth is an implementation of the **Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines** algorithm written in the **R Statistical Language** (see Milborrow 2011).

Euclidian Distance	7
The simple, or straight-line, distance between two points, colloquially described as “as the crow flies.”	
False Negative Rate (FNR).....	70
The fraction of the positive observation (site locations) that are incorrectly classified as a negative observation (site not-likely). The FNR is derived from the Confusion Matrix and calculated by dividing the number of false negatives by total number of observed positive observations. This number is also interpreted as the Type-II error rate, or beta (β).	
False Positive Rate (FPR).....	36
The fraction of the negative observations (background locations) that are incorrectly classified as a positive observations (site likely). The FPR is derived from the Confusion Matrix and calculated by dividing the number of false positives by total number of observed negative observations. This number is also interpreted as the Type-I error rate.	
Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV).....	18
GCV is a statistical method that estimates performance or prediction error from within a model based on weight assigned to model complexity. GCV approximates the measure of performance that would be derived through leave-one-out Cross-Validation . In this project, the GCV relates to the internal performance measure derived from the Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines model (see Milborrow 2014).	
Generalized Linear Models (GLM)	18
GLMs are a family of models that extend linear regression by allowing for error distributions other than the normal distribution. This is achieved by using link functions to relate the response variable to the appropriate error distribution. Logistic Regression and Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines are examples of GLM regression (see Madsen and Thyregod 2011).	
Generalized R-Square (GRSQ).....	53
This metric is used in the Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines model to normalize Generalized Cross-Validation and estimate a model’s R-Squared when predicting for independent data. This measure is a ratio of $1 - \text{GCV}$ divided by the GCV of the Null Model or intercept only model (see Milborrow 2014).	

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	i
A GIS is a computer application that stores, manages, displays, and manipulates information with a spatial component (see Wheatley and Gillings 2002).	
K-folds Cross-Validation	14
Cross-Validation is the method by which a sample of observations is split into a number of different but equal-sized classes. The number of classes is referred to as K and the classes themselves are referred to as folds, hence “K-folds Cross-Validation.” This is a method by which models can be validated on test sets that were not part of the training set, while at the same time, using the entire data set for modeling (see Efron and Tibshirani 1997).	
Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K-S) Test	8
A non-parametric statistical test that measures the equality of continuous unpaired probability distributions to each other (two-sample test) or a reference distribution (one-sample test). In this study, the K-S test is used to test whether the distribution of an environmental variable is significantly different between known site locations and the overall environmental background (see Conover 1999).	
Kvamme Gain (Kg).....	13
The Kg is a metric used to assess the ability of a model to correctly classify positive observations (site present) given the area in which positive observations are predicted to occur (site-likely area). The higher the gain, the greater the ratio of percent sites present to percent of the modeled area considered site-likely. This measure does not take into account model precision or True Positive Rate (Sensitivity) , meaning that an equivalent Kg statistic can be reached by correctly predicting 16% of known sites in 5% of the area or 95% of known sites in 30% of the area (see Kvamme 1988).	
Likelihood Ratio Test	50
This is a statistical test used to compare the fit of two models. In this project, the Likelihood Ratio Test is used to compare Logistic Regression models by testing the likelihood ratios of the Null Model and alternative models. This test uses a p-value to accept or reject the null model based on the likelihood ratio.	
Logistic Regression (LR).....	14
Logistic Regression is a statistical model used to predict for a binary response (0 or 1) or to classify a categorical response (“dead” or “alive”) based on one or more predictors. This method uses a S-shaped logistic transformation to model the binary response probability as the log odds of the linear function of the predictor variables. Simply, the	

model fits the linear model to the S-shaped curve so that the prediction is kept between 0 and 1 (see Pampel 2000).

Mann-Whitney (MW) U Test8

The Mann-Whitney U Test is a non-parametric statistical test that evaluates the dissimilarity of unpaired distributions by ranking the observations and comparing the mean ranks. This test is similar in concept to the **Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test**, but uses a ranked approach as opposed to a distance approach. The MW U Test is more sensitive to changes in the median of two distributions (see Lehman 1975).

Maximum Likelihood Estimate (MLE)50

The MLE is a statistical procedure used to estimate parameters within **Logistic Regression**. This function uses an iterative approach to identify a set of parameters for which the probability of the observed data is the greatest (see Pampel 2000).

Mean Squared Error (MSE)56

The MSE is a statistic, or loss function, used to quantify the difference between an estimate and a true value. In this project, the MSE is used to quantify the difference between the predicted values (\hat{y}) and the observed test values (y). MSE is calculated as the **Sum of Squared Errors** divided by the number of observations (see Lehman and Casella 1998).

Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS).....14

A statistical model that is an extension of the **Generalized Linear Model**. This method approximates a non-linear model by fitting piecewise linear segments that are connected at nodes referred to as hinge functions. The hinge functions provide the point at which the two straight lines join. A sequence of lines and hinges approximates a non-linear **Spline**. The MARS model uses a forward pass to find the best fit that minimizes the **Sum of Squared Error**. This first pass is referred to as “greedy” because it seeks the best fit regardless of how many terms, or line and hinge segments, it creates. To avoid over-fitting, the MARS method has a second pass that prunes the terms created in the first path to assess which can be removed without having large negative effects on the model’s performance; this lowers the model’s complexity and variance. The MARS method uses **Generalized Cross-Validation** to assess how pruning affects performance. This method was introduced by Friedman (1991).

Negative Prediction Gain (NPG)70

The NPG is a statistic that is derived from the confusion matrix to assess a model’s ability to correctly classify site-unlikely areas. The NPG quantifies how much less likely

a site discovery is at a location labeled site-unlikely using the model than if surveying at random. Ideally, a model would have a low NPG and a high **Positive Predictive Gain** (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Negative Prediction Value (NPV)70

The NPV is a measure that is derived from the confusion matrix. This measures the probability that a non-site cell is correctly labeled as a background cell (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Null Model50

The term Null Model refers to a **Logistic Regression** that only contains the response variable (in this case, site prediction), with no predictor. It is essentially a flat-line regression that uses the average of all values, thereby providing a baseline against which the saturated model (that is, the model that incorporates the predictors) can be tested. If the saturated model is not better than the null model by a statistically significant amount (in this case as measured using the **Likelihood Ratio Test**), then new predictors need to be chosen.

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS).....50

OLS is the statistical method most commonly used to estimate unknown parameters within linear regression. OLS seeks to fit a line that minimizes the **Sum of Squared Errors** between the predictor (in this case, the environmental variable) and the response (site-present vs. site-absent).

Out-of-Bag (OOB) Sample19

The term OOB is used to describe the internal testing data set within predictive algorithms such as **Bagging** and **Random Forests**. Within these algorithms, the training data set is sampled via the bootstrap with roughly two-thirds of the data used for model training and the remaining one-third used for testing and variable selection. This remaining one-third is referred to as the OOB Sample. OOB Sample error rates are calculated from this hold-out set (see Breiman 1996b).

Out-of-Sample (OOS).....37

The term OOS refers to the portion of data within the hold-out sample from **K-folds Cross Validation**. For example, in $k = 10$ fold CV, the first pass will use folds 1–9 to train the model and fold 10 to test the model. The tenth fold is the OOS fold and the error estimate derived from this is called the OOS estimate (see Efron and Tibshirani 1997).

Pennsylvania Archaeological Site Survey (PASS).....1
The PASS files are a collection of paper forms, maps, reports, and photographs that document the location and attributes of known archaeological sites within the Commonwealth of Pennsylvania. These files have been digitized and can be accessed through the **Cultural Resources Geographic Information System**.

Positive Predictive Gain (PPG).....36
The PPG is a statistic that is derived from the **Confusion Matrix** to assess a model’s ability to correctly classify site-likely areas. The PPG quantifies how much more likely a site discovery is at a location labeled site-likely using the model than if surveying at random. Ideally, a model would have a high PPG and a low **Negative Prediction Value** (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Positive Prediction Value (PPV).....70
The PPV is a measure that is derived from the **Confusion Matrix**. This measures the probability that a site cell is correctly labeled as a site-likely cell (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Pseudo R-Squared (Pseudo R²).....55
Pseudo R-Squared describes a statistic that is intended to mimic the qualities of the **R-Squared**, but is applicable to models that do not use **Ordinary Least Squares**, such as **Logistic Regression**. In general, Pseudo R-Squared is similar to **R-Squared** in that the numerous variations of the measure range approximately from 0 to 1 and a higher number indicates a generally better fit. However, Pseudo R-Squared should not be compared directly to **R-Squared** because they are derived quite differently. A number of Pseudo R-Squared variations have similarities to the **Likelihood Ratio Test** (see Pampel 2000).

Python Language38
Python is a widely used high-level programming language. (Information available at: <http://www.python.org/>.)

R-Squared (R²).....50
R², also referred to as the Coefficient of Determination, is a metric used in the evaluation of variance and goodness-of-fit for primarily linear models using **Ordinary Least Squares**. The R² is calculated as a one minus the residual sum of squares divided by the total sum of squares. The most common interpretation of R² is for the fit of a linear model. An R² of 1 indicates a perfect fit between the regression line and data points.

R Statistical Language	38
R Statistical Language is a widely used statistical computing environment. (Information available at: http://www.r-project.org/ .)	
Random Forests	14
Random Forests is trademarked statistical classification algorithm created by Leo Breiman and Adele Cutler. Random Forests is a tree based ensemble method that builds off the ideas of Classification and Regression Trees and Bagging . The primary features of Random Forests include internal testing through Bootstrap Aggregating and variable importance via random subset selection (see Breiman 2001).	
randomForest (RF) (see also Random Forests)	18
RF is an implementation of the Random Forests classification algorithm written in the R Statistical Language (see Liaw and Wiener 2002).	
Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC).....	21
The ROC is a graphical representation of statistical classification model results. The ROC graph typically takes on a curved shape and is therefore often referred to as the ROC curve. The x-axis of the ROC graph is a model's False Positive Rate and the y-axis is the True Positive Rate ; both are scaled from 0 to 1. The quantities on the x- and y-axes are also referred to as 1 – Specificity and Sensitivity , respectively. The actual curve in the graphic is generated by calculating the True Positive Rate and False Positive Rate for each cut-point of the model's prediction. The graphic also contains a line (often dashed) that originates at point 0,0 and goes at a 45-degree angle to point 1,1. This line represents a model that has no predictive power. The closer the ROC curve is to the upper left corner of the graph (which is point $x = 0, y = 1$), the greater the predictive power. Put another way, the best classification has the largest area under the curve. A line of this description will have a high True Positive Rate for the entire range of False Positive Rates . The ROC curve can be used to estimate the total predictive power of the model, often enumerated as the Area Under Curve , to compare similar models across all cut-points, or select an optimal cut-point to use for classification, resulting in a Confusion Matrix (see Fawcett 2004).	
Residual Sum-of-Squares (RSS).....	53
The RSS is a measure of the model fit. The RSS is calculated as the sum of squared differences between the estimated and actual observations (see Salkind 2007).	

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).....21
The RMSE is a statistic, or loss function, used to quantify the difference between an estimate and a true value. The RMSE is calculated as the square root of the **Mean Squared Error**. When calculated on **Out-of-Sample** predictions, such as in this project, the RMSE represents the sample standard deviation of the prediction errors. A benefit of RMSE over **Mean Squared Error** is that it is scaled to the dependent variable and is therefore directly interpretable. With a binary dependent variable (0 to 1), the RMSE is taken as the distance on average between the predicted probability and the true value (see Salkind 2007).

Sensitivity (see also **True Positive Rate**)21
Sensitivity is a term used for a classification’s **True Positive Rate**; this value is also referred to as Recall. Sensitivity is the total fraction of sites that are classified by the model to be in the site-likely area. This measure is akin to the concept of precision and Type II errors. Sensitivity is calculated for a cut-point within a classification model as the number of correctly predicted positive observations (correctly classified sites) divided by the total number of actual positive observations (known sites) (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Specificity (see also **True Negative Rate**).....21
Specificity is a termed used for a classification’s **True Negative Rate**. Specificity is the fraction of background that is classified as site-unlikely by the model. This measure is akin to the concept of accuracy and Type I errors. Specificity is calculated for a cut-point within a classification model as the number of correctly predicted negative observations (correctly classified non-sites) divided by the total number of actual negative observations (background cells) (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

Spline18
A curve that connects two or more points. The shape of the Spline is determined by a mathematical function that interpolates the space between the points into a smooth curve.

Sum of Squared Error (SSE).....50
The SSE is a measure of prediction accuracy. This measure is calculated nearly the same as the **Residual Sum-of-Squares**, but more commonly used on prediction errors as opposed to model fit. Within this project, the SSE is used as a part of the **Mean Squared Error** and **Root Mean Square Error** statistics to assess the accuracy of prediction results (see Lehman and Casella 1998).

- True Negative Rate (TNR) (see also **Specificity**).....67
The TNR is a measure of a model’s classification at a given cut-point. Often referred to as a model’s Specificity, the TNR is calculated as the percent of negative observations correctly classified as such. In this project, this would be the rate at which background cells are correctly classified as site un-likely cells (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).
- True Positive Rate (TPR) (see also **Sensitivity**).....67
The TPR is a measure of a model’s classification at a given cut-point. Often referred to as a models Sensitivity, the TPR is calculated as the percent of positive observations correctly classified as such. In this project, this would be the rate at which known site-present cells are correctly classified as site-likely cells (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).
- Unexpected Discovery Rate (UDR).....70
The UDR is a measurement of a model’s classification ability at a given cut-point. The UDR is defined as the probability of a cell containing a site given that the model predicted it as site-unlikely. That can be thought of as the rate of unintentional discovery, or “oops” rate (see Oehlert and Shea 2007).

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APPENDIX B

POTENTIAL PREDICTOR ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABLES

Predictor	Family	Measure	Description
aspect	Topography	bearing	Orientation of slope relative to north
costdist_1	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to historic streams
costdist_2	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to NHD flowlines
costdist_3	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to NHD waterbodies
costdist_4	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to NWI wetlands
costdist_5	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to NWI waterbodies
costdist_6	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to 4th order and higher streams
costdist_7	Hydrology	cost-distance	Cost-distance to 3rd order and higher streams
cst_alo_conf	Hydrology	cost-allocation	Cost-allocation to stream confluence (NHD flowlines)
cst_alo_dranh	Hydrology	cost-allocation	Cost-allocation to stream head (NHD flowlines)
cst_alo_str	Hydrology	cost-allocation	Cost-allocation to streams (NHD flowlines)
cst_alo_str7	Hydrology	cost-allocation	Cost-allocation to 3rd order or higher streams (NHD flowlines)
dem_10m_fill	Topography	elevation, meters (float)	1/3rd Arc-second digital elevation model as float, with sinks filled
dem_10m_int	Topography	elevation, meters (integer)	1/3rd Arc-second digital elevation model as integer, with sinks filled
ed_conflu	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-Distance to stream confluence (NHD flowlines)
ed_drainh	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-Distance to stream heads (NHD flowlines)
ed_hydro_1	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to historic streams
ed_hydro_2	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to NHD flowlines
ed_hydro_3	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to NHD waterbodies
ed_hydro_4	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to NWI wetlands
ed_hydro_5	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to NWI waterbodies
ed_hydro_6	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to 4th order and higher streams
ed_hydro_7	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Euclidian-distance to 3rd order and higher streams

Predictor	Family	Measure	Description
eldrop27c	Topography	elevation, meters	Drop in elevation over 27 cell neighborhood
eldrop3c	Topography	elevation, meters	Drop in elevation over 3 cell neighborhood
eldrop9c	Topography	elevation, meters	Drop in elevation over 9 cell neighborhood
elev_2_conf	Topography - Hydrology	vertical-distance, meters	Elevation to stream confluence (NHD flowlines)
elev_2_drainh	Topography - Hydrology	vertical-distance, meters	Elevation to stream head (NHD flowlines)
elev_2_strm	Topography - Hydrology	vertical-distance, meters	Elevation to stream (NHD flowlines)
flowdir	Hydrology	direction, bearing	Flow direction based on DEM
flw_acum	Hydrology	accumulation, cells	Flow accumulation based on DEM
min_hydro	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Minimum distance to stream or waterbody
min_hydro_wt	Hydrology	euclidian-distance, meters	Minimum distance to stream, waterbody, or wetland
random	Random	random float (0 to 1)	Randomly selected number between 1 and 0
rng_16c	Topography	elevation range, integer	Range of elevation in 16 cell neighborhood
rng_1c	Topography	elevation range, integer	Range of elevation in 1 cell neighborhood
rng_32c	Topography	elevation range, integer	Range of elevation in 32 cell neighborhood
rng_4c	Topography	elevation range, integer	Range of elevation in 4 cell neighborhood
rng_8c	Topography	elevation range, integer	Range of elevation in 8 cell neighborhood
slope_deg	Topography	slope, degrees	Topographic slope measured in degrees
slope_pct	Topography	slope, percent	Topographic slope measured in percent rise over run
slpvr_16c	Topography	slope range, integer	Slope variability within 16 cell neighborhood
slpvr_1c	Topography	slope range, integer	Slope variability within 1 cell neighborhood
slpvr_32c	Topography	slope range, integer	Slope variability within 32 cell neighborhood

Predictor	Family	Measure	Description
slpvr_4c	Topography	slope range, integer	Slope variability within 4 cell neighborhood
slpvr_8c	Topography	slope range, integer	Slope variability within 8 cell neighborhood
std_16c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of elevation range within 16 cell neighborhood
std_1c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of elevation range within 1 cell neighborhood
std_32c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of elevation range within 32 cell neighborhood
std_4c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of elevation range within 4 cell neighborhood
std_8c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of elevation range within 8 cell neighborhood
tpi_10c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Position Index. Position of cell relative to surrounding landscape within 10 cell neighborhood
tpi_50c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Position Index. Position of cell relative to surrounding landscape within 50 cell neighborhood
tpi_5c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Position Index. Position of cell relative to surrounding landscape within 5 cell neighborhood
tpi_cls10c	Topography	classification, nominal	TPI standardized and classified into 1 standard deviation groups within 10 cell neighborhood
tpi_cls50c	Topography	classification, nominal	TPI standardized and classified into 1 standard deviation groups within 50 cell neighborhood
tpi_cls5c	Topography	classification, nominal	TPI standardized and classified into 1 standard deviation groups within 5 cell neighborhood
tpi_sd10c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of TPI within 10 cell neighborhood
tpi_sd50c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of TPI within 50 cell neighborhood
tpi_sd5c	Topography	standard deviation	Standard deviation of TPI within 5 cell neighborhood

Predictor	Family	Measure	Description
tri_16c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Ruggedness Index. Measure of terrain roughness within 16 cell neighborhood
tri_1c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Ruggedness Index. Measure of terrain roughness within 1 cell neighborhood
tri_32c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Ruggedness Index. Measure of terrain roughness within 32 cell neighborhood
tri_4c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Ruggedness Index. Measure of terrain roughness within 4 cell neighborhood
tri_8c	Topography	index, integer	Topographic Ruggedness Index. Measure of terrain roughness within 8 cell neighborhood
twi27c	Topography - Hydrology	index, integer	Topographic Wetness Index. Measure of upslope accumulation within 27 cell neighborhood
twi3c	Topography - Hydrology	index, integer	Topographic Wetness Index. Measure of upslope accumulation within 3 cell neighborhood
twi9c	Topography - Hydrology	index, integer	Topographic Wetness Index. Measure of upslope accumulation within 9 cell neighborhood
vrf_27c	Topography	index, integer	Vector Roughness Factor. Measure of three-dimensional variation in slope within 27 cell neighborhood
vrf_3c	Topography	index, integer	Vector Roughness Factor. Measure of three-dimensional variation in slope within 3 cell neighborhood
vrf_9c	Topography	index, integer	Vector Roughness Factor. Measure of three-dimensional variation in slope within 9 cell neighborhood

APPENDIX C

FINAL MODEL SITE AND BACKGROUND PERCENTAGES

Riverine Region 1

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.01	0.01	-0.96	1.46	0.03	0.98
0.95	0.00	0.07	n/a	8.21	0.30	0.96	8.78	0.19	0.98
0.9	0.29	0.24	0.16	17.06	0.70	0.96	29.17	0.66	0.98
0.85	3.56	0.69	0.81	27.94	1.36	0.95	54.79	1.43	0.97
0.8	9.50	1.36	0.86	35.37	2.08	0.94	69.79	2.07	0.97
0.75	18.80	2.25	0.88	41.40	2.86	0.93	80.92	2.73	0.97
0.7	30.34	3.49	0.89	48.36	3.84	0.92	88.37	3.28	0.96
0.65	42.92	5.06	0.88	54.65	4.89	0.91	92.50	3.71	0.96
0.6	54.38	6.85	0.87	60.95	6.00	0.90	95.74	4.23	0.96
0.55	64.20	8.68	0.86	66.77	7.24	0.89	98.12	5.09	0.95
0.5	71.58	10.67	0.85	71.18	8.65	0.88	99.12	5.70	0.94
0.45	76.55	12.68	0.83	75.41	10.30	0.86	99.73	6.38	0.94
0.4	81.58	15.13	0.81	79.39	12.07	0.85	99.95	7.20	0.93
0.35	86.14	18.11	0.79	82.93	14.24	0.83	99.99	8.25	0.92
0.3	89.29	21.26	0.76	86.46	16.82	0.81	100.00	9.72	0.90
0.25	91.57	25.17	0.73	90.31	19.93	0.78	100.00	11.72	0.88
0.2	93.54	30.03	0.68	93.00	23.90	0.74	100.00	14.41	0.86
0.15	95.74	36.30	0.62	95.40	29.96	0.69	100.00	18.42	0.82
0.1	97.83	45.81	0.53	97.89	40.91	0.58	100.00	26.07	0.74
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Riverine Region 2

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	1.31	0.03	0.98	37.19	0.25	0.99
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	13.21	0.18	0.99	55.63	0.38	0.99
0.9	0.00	0.08	n/a	22.76	0.34	0.98	67.46	0.48	0.99
0.85	0.00	0.22	n/a	27.63	0.49	0.98	76.61	0.56	0.99
0.8	3.05	0.40	0.87	30.65	0.63	0.98	82.56	0.64	0.99
0.75	15.45	0.61	0.96	32.89	0.81	0.98	87.53	0.72	0.99
0.7	24.77	0.86	0.97	36.94	1.03	0.97	91.22	0.81	0.99
0.65	29.25	1.12	0.96	41.24	1.33	0.97	95.39	0.93	0.99
0.6	35.32	1.43	0.96	46.42	1.71	0.96	98.24	1.07	0.99
0.55	38.46	1.72	0.96	51.16	2.15	0.96	99.23	1.21	0.99
0.5	39.10	2.20	0.94	55.13	2.66	0.95	99.66	1.38	0.99
0.45	39.77	2.81	0.93	59.12	3.23	0.95	99.95	1.58	0.98
0.4	43.76	3.58	0.92	62.90	3.86	0.94	100.00	1.84	0.98
0.35	47.78	4.66	0.90	65.68	4.61	0.93	100.00	2.17	0.98
0.3	53.58	6.32	0.88	69.10	5.68	0.92	100.00	2.64	0.97
0.25	64.82	8.76	0.86	72.65	6.94	0.90	100.00	3.34	0.97
0.2	71.65	13.08	0.82	78.41	8.98	0.89	100.00	4.48	0.96
0.15	87.01	21.63	0.75	85.16	13.29	0.84	100.00	6.52	0.93
0.1	91.31	46.82	0.49	91.68	27.34	0.70	100.00	11.39	0.89
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	1.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	0.00	1.00	100.00	0.00	1.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Riverine Region 3

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.14	0.00	0.97
0.95	0.00	0.01	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	2.03	0.07	0.97
0.9	0.01	0.03	-1.00	0.00	0.00	n/a	6.86	0.23	0.97
0.85	0.14	0.08	0.43	0.00	0.00	n/a	13.99	0.48	0.97
0.8	0.55	0.16	0.72	0.05	0.01	0.77	24.25	0.85	0.97
0.75	0.75	0.22	0.71	0.31	0.04	0.86	35.58	1.29	0.96
0.7	1.34	0.33	0.76	0.64	0.09	0.86	45.84	1.75	0.96
0.65	1.91	0.50	0.74	2.92	0.30	0.90	54.64	2.22	0.96
0.6	3.15	0.96	0.69	5.08	0.73	0.86	65.30	2.89	0.96
0.55	6.29	1.97	0.69	12.02	1.97	0.84	76.32	3.75	0.95
0.5	8.99	3.00	0.67	26.36	4.55	0.83	85.46	4.79	0.94
0.45	15.57	5.34	0.66	38.39	7.70	0.80	91.62	6.08	0.93
0.4	25.48	7.78	0.69	48.80	11.13	0.77	95.77	7.73	0.92
0.35	32.50	9.86	0.70	60.35	14.74	0.76	97.80	9.77	0.90
0.3	46.03	13.80	0.70	71.02	18.50	0.74	98.90	12.27	0.88
0.25	56.18	18.18	0.68	81.26	22.78	0.72	99.59	15.28	0.85
0.2	74.69	27.56	0.63	88.40	27.42	0.69	99.95	18.90	0.81
0.15	94.27	45.32	0.52	91.42	31.90	0.65	100.00	23.79	0.76
0.1	98.66	66.41	0.33	94.56	39.14	0.59	100.00	31.57	0.68
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Riverine Region 4

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.11	0.00	0.99	0.22	0.00	0.99
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.14	0.01	0.96	3.21	0.01	1.00
0.9	0.00	0.00	n/a	2.32	0.11	0.95	9.44	0.04	1.00
0.85	0.00	0.01	n/a	5.04	0.32	0.94	17.41	0.08	1.00
0.8	0.00	0.03	n/a	9.49	0.62	0.93	31.64	0.17	0.99
0.75	0.00	0.07	n/a	15.62	1.00	0.94	59.40	0.57	0.99
0.7	0.00	0.20	n/a	20.64	1.42	0.93	75.81	1.08	0.99
0.65	0.00	0.40	n/a	26.54	1.90	0.93	88.75	1.70	0.98
0.6	0.29	0.69	-1.35	33.15	2.49	0.92	93.71	2.05	0.98
0.55	8.22	1.45	0.82	40.58	3.22	0.92	96.88	2.35	0.98
0.5	22.22	3.04	0.86	48.00	4.16	0.91	98.49	2.68	0.97
0.45	45.91	5.43	0.88	55.21	5.37	0.90	99.51	3.11	0.97
0.4	55.00	7.75	0.86	64.24	6.97	0.89	99.81	3.70	0.96
0.35	63.90	10.57	0.83	72.21	8.92	0.88	99.98	4.45	0.96
0.3	68.24	13.73	0.80	77.07	11.34	0.85	100.00	5.41	0.95
0.25	82.59	18.98	0.77	80.12	14.29	0.82	100.00	6.90	0.93
0.2	87.93	24.59	0.72	85.79	18.31	0.79	100.00	9.07	0.91
0.15	95.84	32.16	0.66	93.71	23.93	0.74	100.00	12.51	0.87
0.1	97.96	41.01	0.58	98.33	32.31	0.67	100.00	19.73	0.80
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Riverine Region 5

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	8.83	0.09	0.99
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	19.31	0.25	0.99
0.9	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	28.74	0.47	0.98
0.85	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.55	0.05	0.91	39.10	0.83	0.98
0.8	0.00	0.00	n/a	1.90	0.17	0.91	50.09	1.40	0.97
0.75	0.00	0.00	n/a	4.09	0.57	0.86	60.53	2.23	0.96
0.7	0.00	0.00	n/a	9.05	2.09	0.77	69.43	3.34	0.95
0.65	0.00	0.00	n/a	16.58	5.12	0.69	76.99	4.72	0.94
0.6	0.00	0.00	n/a	26.87	8.69	0.68	90.67	8.70	0.90
0.55	0.87	0.15	0.83	43.69	14.61	0.67	94.95	10.71	0.89
0.5	25.40	8.31	0.67	52.41	19.76	0.62	97.79	13.11	0.87
0.45	48.84	18.63	0.62	62.46	26.46	0.58	99.17	15.90	0.84
0.4	72.05	35.36	0.51	71.85	32.84	0.54	99.83	19.23	0.81
0.35	77.60	45.38	0.42	79.88	39.53	0.51	99.96	22.95	0.77
0.3	86.65	58.43	0.33	85.60	46.57	0.46	99.99	26.93	0.73
0.25	90.79	66.34	0.27	89.67	54.77	0.39	100.00	31.47	0.69
0.2	92.06	75.91	0.18	93.96	68.27	0.27	100.00	37.20	0.63
0.15	96.37	80.71	0.16	97.79	85.72	0.12	100.00	44.91	0.55
0.1	99.16	87.61	0.12	99.98	96.31	0.04	100.00	58.37	0.42
0.05	99.69	93.68	0.06	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Upland Region 2

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	0.00	n/a	40.29	0.00	1.00
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.53	0.01	0.99	63.67	0.00	1.00
0.9	0.00	0.00	n/a	1.98	0.01	1.00	75.96	0.01	1.00
0.85	0.00	0.00	n/a	2.64	0.01	1.00	84.68	0.01	1.00
0.8	0.00	0.00	n/a	3.17	0.01	1.00	91.15	0.01	1.00
0.75	0.00	0.00	n/a	4.89	0.02	1.00	95.11	0.01	1.00
0.7	0.00	0.00	n/a	5.68	0.02	1.00	96.83	0.01	1.00
0.65	0.00	0.00	n/a	6.87	0.03	1.00	98.68	0.01	1.00
0.6	0.00	0.00	n/a	8.59	0.05	0.99	99.87	0.02	1.00
0.55	0.00	0.00	n/a	9.91	0.07	0.99	100.00	0.02	1.00
0.5	0.00	0.00	n/a	11.36	0.11	0.99	100.00	0.02	1.00
0.45	0.00	0.00	n/a	12.42	0.18	0.99	100.00	0.03	1.00
0.4	0.00	0.00	n/a	14.27	0.28	0.98	100.00	0.04	1.00
0.35	0.00	0.00	n/a	19.95	0.42	0.98	100.00	0.05	1.00
0.3	0.00	0.00	n/a	29.59	0.63	0.98	100.00	0.07	1.00
0.25	0.00	0.00	n/a	41.74	0.95	0.98	100.00	0.11	1.00
0.2	0.00	0.00	n/a	54.43	1.44	0.97	100.00	0.18	1.00
0.15	0.00	0.00	n/a	62.22	2.33	0.96	100.00	0.35	1.00
0.1	0.13	0.03	0.78	66.84	4.69	0.93	100.00	1.02	0.99
0.05	4.49	4.39	0.02	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Upland Region 4

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0	0	n/a	12.29	0.06	0.99	48.42	0.01	1.00
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	15.68	0.12	0.99	66.63	0.02	1.00
0.9	0.00	0.01	n/a	19.42	0.17	0.99	79.02	0.02	1.00
0.85	0.00	0.02	n/a	23.26	0.23	0.99	86.31	0.03	1.00
0.8	0.00	0.03	n/a	29.18	0.29	0.99	91.16	0.05	1.00
0.75	0.00	0.05	n/a	32.16	0.36	0.99	94.96	0.06	1.00
0.7	0.00	0.09	n/a	34.35	0.44	0.99	96.74	0.08	1.00
0.65	4.18	0.14	0.97	36.47	0.53	0.99	98.32	0.11	1.00
0.6	9.13	0.21	0.98	38.59	0.64	0.98	99.30	0.14	1.00
0.55	11.34	0.32	0.97	40.62	0.76	0.98	99.81	0.17	1.00
0.5	12.93	0.49	0.96	42.43	0.91	0.98	99.94	0.22	1.00
0.45	17.21	0.74	0.96	43.69	1.10	0.97	100.00	0.27	1.00
0.4	22.97	1.15	0.95	45.25	1.33	0.97	100.00	0.35	1.00
0.35	33.05	1.82	0.94	47.02	1.63	0.97	100.00	0.46	1.00
0.3	47.34	2.97	0.94	48.86	2.04	0.96	100.00	0.62	0.99
0.25	59.13	4.96	0.92	53.04	2.64	0.95	100.00	0.87	0.99
0.2	66.22	8.59	0.87	55.10	3.64	0.93	100.00	1.29	0.99
0.15	67.33	15.71	0.77	58.49	5.59	0.90	100.00	2.15	0.98
0.1	84.09	30.58	0.64	68.69	11.81	0.83	100.00	4.65	0.95
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

Upland Region 5

Probability	LR			Adaptive Regression Splines (Earth)			RF		
	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg	% Sites	% Area	Kg
1	0.00	0.00	n/a	47.40	0.09	1.00	68.61	0.05	1.00
0.95	0.00	0.00	n/a	50.75	0.11	1.00	80.24	0.06	1.00
0.9	0.24	0.03	0.88	50.78	0.15	1.00	87.99	0.08	1.00
0.85	1.21	0.13	0.89	50.84	0.17	1.00	92.64	0.09	1.00
0.8	13.42	0.37	0.97	50.90	0.20	1.00	95.71	0.11	1.00
0.75	32.76	0.69	0.98	50.92	0.22	1.00	97.78	0.13	1.00
0.7	50.82	1.12	0.98	50.93	0.25	1.00	98.93	0.16	1.00
0.65	52.84	1.60	0.97	50.95	0.30	0.99	99.62	0.19	1.00
0.6	53.09	2.20	0.96	51.11	0.36	0.99	99.95	0.23	1.00
0.55	53.35	3.02	0.94	51.58	0.46	0.99	99.99	0.29	1.00
0.5	54.03	4.19	0.92	52.10	0.68	0.99	100.00	0.37	1.00
0.45	54.17	5.79	0.89	53.87	1.14	0.98	100.00	0.48	1.00
0.4	55.85	7.88	0.86	56.82	2.11	0.96	100.00	0.65	0.99
0.35	59.42	10.44	0.82	61.22	3.96	0.94	100.00	0.90	0.99
0.3	64.55	13.98	0.78	66.99	7.25	0.89	100.00	1.32	0.99
0.25	71.87	19.22	0.73	75.51	12.78	0.83	100.00	2.03	0.98
0.2	76.88	26.96	0.65	84.41	21.00	0.75	100.00	3.37	0.97
0.15	84.80	38.27	0.55	90.95	32.95	0.64	100.00	6.28	0.94
0.1	96.98	53.81	0.45	97.36	49.98	0.49	100.00	14.03	0.86
0.05	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00
0	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00

APPENDIX D

FINAL SENSITIVITY ASSESSMENT MODEL ATLAS

FOR PILOT MODEL AREA

(SCALE 1:105,000)

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 1

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 2

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 3

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 4

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 5

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 6

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 7

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 8

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 9

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 10

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 11

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 12

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 13

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 14

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 15

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 16

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 17

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 18

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 19

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 20

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 21

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 22

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 23

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 24

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 25

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 26

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 27

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 28

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 29

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3

Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 30

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 31

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 32

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 33

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 34

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 35

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 36

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

Pennsylvania Predictive Model Set: Task 3
Final Pilot Model Sensitivity Assessment

Map Page: 37

1:105,000

Sensitivity

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Steep >15% Slope
- Water
- PASS Site
- Map Page Boundary

